

GEN

GENDEX Data Analysis of the Gender & Diversity Scorecard

Deliverable D3.3

March, 2025

DEX

Funded by
the European Union

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Glossary of Terms	4
Executive summary	7
1 Introduction	10
1.1 Overview	10
2 Background.....	12
2.1 The EIC.....	12
2.2 GENDEX.....	12
2.3 Key elements of the pilot Gender & Diversity Index.....	13
3 Gender & Diversity Validated Index Scorecard: Results analysis	19
3.1 Deep tech talent tier	19
3.2 Intellectual and social capital tier	26
3.3 Asset and investment tier	43
3.4 Investor tier	63
4 Final Conclusions and Key Recommendations	69
4.1 Key insights	69
4.2 Recommendations for stakeholders	75
4.3 What's next?.....	80
4.4 Acknowledgements	82
ANNEX 1 Methodology and Limitations	83
4.5 Key definitions.....	83
4.6 Analysis through secondary sources	86
4.7 Analysis on primary sources.....	92
ANNEX 2 Primary Research Data collection Tools	95
Survey questionnaire.....	95
4.8 Interview guide for start-up and scale-up founders	105
4.9 Interview guide for investors	106
Annex 3 Presentation on Key gendex Hypothesis and data highlights	107
5 The Partners	117

Title	Document Version
D3.3 GENDEX Data Analysis of the Gender & Diversity Scorecard	1.2

Project Number	Project Acronym	Project Title
101105161	GENDEX	Gender & Diversity Index for a fair, competitive, resilient and sustainable Europe

Contract Delivery Date		Deliverable Type
M7 (August 2024)	M13 (January 2025)	R-PU

Responsible	Organization	Contributing WP
Andrea Siviero	IDC	WP3

Authors	Organisation
Martina Longo	IDC Italy
Erica Spinoni	IDC Italy
Meike Escherich	IDC UK
Zuzana Kovacova	IDC CEMA
Tanya Suarez	BluSpecs

Abstract
<p>D3.3 Data Analysis of the Gender & Diversity Scorecard analyses the final results of the data gathered for the European innovation gender and diversity index presented in D3.2 Validated Gender & Diversity Index Scorecard.</p> <p>The aim of this report is to analyse the data gathered for the index to identify gender gaps in the European innovation and entrepreneurship landscape, specifically in deep tech areas in scope for the European Innovation Council (EIC), with a view to providing conclusions and actionable recommendations for key stakeholders – from investors to policy-makers.</p>

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Advanced connectivity, navigation and digital technologies	A broad range of technologies that include 5G/6G, fibre and IoT to provide high-speed data pathways; navigation (enhanced GPS, LiDAR and AR) to enable precise location awareness; digital technologies (cloud, big data, cybersecurity and blockchain) to power intelligent applications and automation
Advanced materials, manufacturing and recycling technologies	Advanced materials encompass novel substances with enhanced properties; advanced manufacturing employs innovative processes for efficient production; and advanced recycling develops methods to recover and reuse materials, minimizing waste and promoting circularity.
Advanced sensing technologies	Advanced sensing technologies (e.g., infrared) detect and measure physical or chemical properties with increased accuracy, sensitivity and speed, often in real time. They provide critical data for applications ranging from environmental monitoring and healthcare to autonomous systems and industrial automation.
AI technologies	A broad range of computational methods designed to mimic human cognitive functions (e.g., learning, problem-solving and decision-making)
Angel investor	An individual who provides capital to early-stage companies, typically start-ups, in exchange for equity ownership
Biotechnology	The use of living organisms and biological systems to create products and technologies for medical, agricultural and environmental applications
Bootstrapping	The process of funding and running a company using only personal finances or operating revenue
Burn rate	A financial metric that describes how quickly a company is spending its cash reserves to finance its overhead before generating positive cash flow. Typically expressed as the amount of cash spent per month (monthly burn rate)
Buy-out	An operation where an investment funds or a company acquires the majority of the company, changing the organizational structure, with the aim of managing the organization
Cliff	A specific period of time that an employee must work at the company before they become entitled to any portion of their stock options, restricted stock units (RSUs) or other equity compensation
Climate tech	Climate technology encompasses a broad range of technologies aimed at addressing climate change.
DEI	Diversity, equity and inclusion

Diversity	Diversity refers to the presence of differences within a given setting. This can include differences in race, ethnicity, gender, age, sexual orientation, disability, religion, socioeconomic status and other attributes.
Early VC	The next phase after seed rounds (Series A to Series B rounds), where more established VC firms and corporations may begin to invest
EIC	European Innovation Council
EISMEA	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
EU	European Union
Family office	A private company that manages the financial and personal affairs of a wealthy family or individual
Founder	An individual who initiates and establishes the creation of a new business venture, either alone or with a co-founder with complementary skill sets and/or networks
GENDEX	The first pan-European innovation gender and diversity index
GP	General partner – an individual responsible for raising capital from limited partners, deploying that capital into investments, and ultimately managing the portfolio of companies in VCs
IPO	Initial public offering – the first time a private company offers shares of its stock to the general public, marking its transition from private to public ownership
Later stage VC	Investment rounds from Series C to Series E
LP	Limited partner – entities providing the capital needed for investments. They are passive investors and do not have day-to-day control or involvement in the venture fund.
Men-led company	A company with only men as key executives or board members
Merger	A strategic business transaction where two or more companies voluntarily combine to form a single new entity
PE	Private equity – an investment firm that invests in privately held companies
Pre-seed and seed	The earliest stages of funding which helps a start-up grow
Quantum technologies	A range of technologies that utilize quantum mechanics in computing, communication, sensing and simulation
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
Robotics and autonomous systems	A range of technologies that combine mechanics, electronics and software to create machines that can perform tasks with varying levels of independence

Runway	The amount of time a company, typically a start-up, has before it runs out of cash, assuming its current spending rate remains constant
Scale-up	A company experiencing a period of rapid growth, requiring Series A or Series B funding
Space and propulsion technologies	A range of technologies that encompass the development and application of systems for travelling to and operating in space. This includes spacecraft design, rocket propulsion, satellite systems and related infrastructure for exploration, communication and scientific research beyond Earth.
Start-up	A company in the initial stages of operation, often characterised by high uncertainty and the need for seed or angel investments
Unicorn	Privately held start-up valued at over \$1 billion, often mature enough for IPOs or significant acquisition events
Venture growth stage	Any financing in the sample that is Series E or later
Vesting schedule	The timeline over which employees or founders gain ownership rights to their shares or stock options
VC	Venture capital – a type of investment firm that provides funding to early-stage companies, typically start-ups, with high growth potential
Women-led company	A company with at least one woman as a key executive or board member, including founders/co-founders

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The European Innovation Council is a flagship initiative of the European Union designed to identify and support breakthrough technologies and game-changing innovations. The EIC operates within the framework of Horizon Europe, which has made gender equality a cross-cutting priority, with initiatives such as the Gender Equality Plan (GEP).

Funded by the European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive, GENDEX aimed to create a comprehensive and actionable index for the European innovation landscape, - and in deep tech areas of addressing significant gender disparities in leadership positions and investment sectors across the deep tech ecosystem. This report analyses the main outcomes of the developed Gender & Diversity Index, to identify gaps in gender diversity and inclusion in the European innovation and entrepreneurship landscape, specifically in deep tech areas of interest for the European Innovation Council. It also provides actionable insights and recommendations for key stakeholders across the European innovation ecosystem, from investors to policy-makers.

Chapter 1 introduces the purpose of this deliverable, while **Chapter 2** provides the background to GENDEX and highlights the key elements of the pilot Gender & Diversity Index, detailing the list of different indicators across the tiers identified for the Index:

1. Deep tech talent tier
2. Intellectual and social capital tier
3. Asset and investment tier
4. Investor tier

Chapter 3 is the core of the report and provides a comprehensive analysis of the Gender and Diversity Index indicators across the four tiers:

Deep tech talent tier

This section provides details on the gender gap in terms of the availability of the STEM talent pool in the European innovation ecosystem. In 2022, the proportion of women among STEM graduates in the European Union neared gender parity, with women making up 42% of all STEM graduates in the region. However, the gender gap remains pronounced in two of the fast-growing deep tech disciplines most closely associated with the creation of scalable start-ups, engineering and ICT (accounting for only 28% and 25% of women graduates respectively). Eurostat data also show modest progress in achieving gender balance among STEM researchers, with the proportion of women STEM researchers at 31%, up only slightly from 30% in 2017. Women also remain significantly under-represented in high-level academic positions, with only 20-25% of academic leadership positions in STEM disciplines at leading universities held by women.

The gender distribution of STEM employment outside academia is more in line with the proportion of STEM graduates from universities. In 2022, women made up 41% of the workforce of scientists and engineers in both the public and private sectors. However, despite ongoing initiatives aimed at fostering growth in science and technology, the data show little change since 2017.

Investment and social capital tier

The intellectual and social capital tier examines the participation and role of women in the business and research communities and shows the societal and intellectual contributions of women in various high-impact fields in the technology and deep tech ecosystems.

Data show that women founders in deep tech hold significantly less intellectual property rights than their men counterparts. Research by GENDEX shows that, over the past decade, only 24% of patent applications in Europe included women as inventors. Women founders in deep tech are more likely to develop intellectual property independently rather than transferring it from previous companies or research institutions – a common pathway for men.

Successful founders draw on deep domain expertise and networks developed throughout their careers. Therefore, the proportion of women employed in top tech companies (the Magnificent 7) and unicorns can be a useful proxy for women-led, scalable deep tech companies. Here, companies that focus on more industrial sectors appear to have lower proportions of women employees, according to GENDEX estimates. Examples include Apple (37 per cent), Meta (20 per cent), Tesla (18 per cent), Personio (38 per cent), Helsing (22 per cent) and Mistral AI (20 per cent), but in any case they are still far from gender parity.

The gender gap in the European deep tech ecosystem is quite pronounced. On average, only 22% of deep tech companies in the EU and UK are women-led, increasing by two percentage points between 2014 and 2024. In terms of European deep tech technology areas, biotechnologies, robotics and autonomous systems and quantum technologies currently have the highest share of women-led companies.

Women-led companies also tend to receive less favourable term sheets than men-led companies. On average, it takes women-led start-ups over 12 months to raise their first cheque, compared with just seven months for men-led companies. The average valuation in the first closed investment round for women-led deep tech start-ups was also around 2.4 times lower than for men-led start-ups over the 2014-2024 period. Looking at terms sheets, the proportion of women receiving a very favourable three-year vesting with a six-month cliff was a third of that of men: 12% vs. 28%. Women founders' experiences and concerns about potential bias, discrimination or harassment in the investment ecosystem lead women to seek alternative routes (e.g. professional associations, early customers, national agencies or business associations) to support their business development. While these alternative routes can be effective, they can also extend the time it takes to raise external funding, leading to prolonged bootstrapping.

Asset and Investment tier

This tier focuses on presenting data on the systemic gender gap in investment raised and value generated by women-led companies in deep tech.

On average, women-led companies closed one deal for every three closed by men-led companies, highlighting the smaller number of opportunities they have to access and close deals. The biotechnology sector sees a higher share of closed rounds for women-led companies, with an average of 10% more deals than the overall women-led average. Concerning down-rounds, the data for both women- and men-led companies is similar, with an average of 9% of total rounds over the 10-year period analysed. However, in years in which VC funding contracted (e.g., 2023), women appear to have a slightly higher proportion of down rounds than men: 14% vs. 12%.

In 2024, GENDEX records only 4 women-led unicorns in the Deep Tech area of scope for the EIC, compared to 26 male-led unicorns. At the same time, the median time to reach unicorn status for men-led organisations is five years, compared to six years for women-led organisations.

Some data points (valuations at non-IPO and IPO exits) suggest better outcomes for women-led companies instead. Over the 10-year period analysed, men-led companies' IPO rate was 10 times that of women-led companies, accounting for 8% of the 150 IPOs registered in the 2014-2024 period. In contrast, average company IPO valuations were 34% higher for women-led companies compared with those led by men. Concerning non-IPO exits, men-led companies' non-IPO rate was 16 times that of women-led companies. However, while the median valuation of non-IPO exits is €53 million, compared with €2.1 billion for men-led companies, the average value of pre-non IPO exit valuations is 33% higher for women-led companies than for men-led companies.

Rather than suggesting that women-led businesses inherently command higher valuations, this trend is more likely to reflect a survival bias - only the most resilient, high-performing women-led businesses make it to exit.

Investor tier

The investor tier focuses on bridging the gender gap in funding, and on the role and presence of women investors in Europe's deep tech innovation ecosystem.

In 2024, the proportion of women partners in investment firms with an EU and UK remit was 16% for venture capital firms and 14% for private equity firms. This under-representation of women investors, together with the wider gender bias in deep tech, is likely to hinder investment in women-led firms. Unfortunately, there has been little change since 2014, with the proportion of female decision-makers in private equity firms falling by 2-3 percentage points. Over the past decade, the share of women angel investors in deep tech has remained stable at only around 7%.

The percentage of investments going to women-led companies also decreased from 2014 to 2024, even if the actual number of companies receiving funding increased over the same period. Inequalities in access to finance contribute significantly to the gender gap in European deep tech, especially for women starting new ventures.

It is clear that action is needed to close the gender gap in the European innovation ecosystem.

Chapter 4 presents the final conclusions and key recommendations that GENDEX proposes to stakeholders based on the Gender and Diversity Index, specifically tailored for policy makers and investors. Future actions to improve the index are also provided.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview

1.1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this deliverable is to present an analysis of and key conclusions on the first Gender & Diversity Index as the final output of the EIC-EISMEA-funded GENDEX project.

As part of the scope, the report aims to identify gaps in gender diversity and inclusion in the European innovation and entrepreneurship landscape, specifically in deep tech areas of interest for the European Innovation Council. The themes analysed range from talent pool availability to access to capital, intellectual property (IP) ownership, representation in the workplace and overall business performance. Gender representation in investment firms is also within scope. The data relates to indicators selected in D3.2 Validated Gender & Diversity Index Scorecard, which provided a framework for measuring the flow of women from the early stages of the tech founder funnel through to the initial public offering stage. This framework has been validated by a group of 12 renowned experts, including policy-makers, investors, corporate leaders and EIC board members. Gender diversity is not just a matter of social equity but a critical driver of innovation within the European ecosystem. A lack of diverse perspectives, including those of women, stifles creativity, limits market understanding and shrinks the available talent pool, ultimately hindering economic growth. Quantitative data (e.g., on the representation of women in STEM fields, leadership positions and patent applications) are essential to understand the scope of the challenge, identify areas for intervention and track the impact of implemented policies. The indicators and metrics presented in this report provide a baseline against which to measure progress and highlight persistent gaps.

The report offers key conclusions drawn from an analysis of the index; it also provides actionable insights and recommendations for key stakeholders across the European innovation ecosystem, from investors to policy-makers.

1.1.2 Structure

This report is divided into six sections:

1. **Introduction:** Overview of the purpose, scope and structure of the document
2. **Background:** Context regarding the GENDEX project and where this deliverable fits into its overall scheme, including a summary of the Gender & Diversity Index framework
3. **Gender & Diversity Validated Index Scorecard result analysis:** Presentation of the key findings for indicators and metrics from the Gender & Diversity Index scorecard
4. **Final conclusions and key recommendations:** Key takeaways from the analysis and index and recommendations for stakeholders, including future actions to improve the index
5. **Annex 1: Methodology and limitations:** Overview of the methodology and limitations on data collection and analysis for the Gender & Diversity Index, divided by secondary and primary sources
6. **Annex 2:** Data collection tools for primary research activities

1.1.3 Related deliverables and reports

- D1.1 Report on the State of the Art: Provides an overview of the definition of diversity and the application within the context of GENDEX, a review of existing global literature and recommendation for an assessment framework and indicators that compose the Gender & Diversity Index
- D1.2 Gender & Diversity Scorecard v1.0: Features the validated set of indicators to measure diversity, identify gaps and enable action to be taken by actors across the European innovation and entrepreneurship landscape
- D2.1 Data Collection Tools: Provides a detailed overview of the primary research to be conducted through interviews and surveys, including the interview guide for investors and founders
- D2.2 Quantitative Survey Results: Provides all the survey-based banner tables and quantitative results for the GENDEX survey. The survey results also feed into the Gender & Diversity scorecard.
- D2.3 Qualitative Interview Results: Summarises key highlights from interviews conducted with 20 women (12 start-up and scale-up founders and co-founders and eight VC investors) to provide qualitative evidence of the gender diversity gap in the European innovation ecosystem
- D3.1 Gender & Diversity Scorecard Results v2.0: Presents the draft version of the European innovation Gender & Diversity Index populated with data
- D3.2 Validated Gender & Diversity Index Scorecard: Presents the final version of the index, validated with the EIC and expert community

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 The EIC

The European Innovation Council is a flagship initiative of the European Union designed to identify and support breakthrough technologies and game-changing innovations. With a budget of €10.1 billion, the EIC supports deep tech and disruptive innovations throughout their life cycle, from early-stage research to proof of concept, technology transfer, and the financing and scaling up of start-ups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)¹.

Support from EIC is provided through three core schemes:

- The EIC Pathfinder for early-stage research and the development of future and emerging technologies
- The EIC Transition for the transformation of novel technologies from the laboratory to real-world applications
- The EIC Accelerator for individual companies, particularly start-ups and SMEs, to develop and scale up their highly innovative products, services or processes²

In 2023, the EIC Fund, the investment arm of the EIC, made over 100 investments worth around €1.2 billion in deep tech companies. The overall portfolio of EIC-supported companies, including those from the pilot and predecessor, has a total value of almost €70 billion³.

Beyond funding, the EIC offers business acceleration services, including coaching, mentoring, access to investors and corporates, and support in navigating regulatory hurdles.

2.2 GENDEX

GENDEX aimed to create a comprehensive and actionable index for the European innovation landscape, addressing significant gender disparities in leadership positions and investment sectors across the deep tech ecosystem. By providing detailed data on gender diversity and its impact on the innovation ecosystem, GENDEX sought to empower investors and policymakers to make informed decisions that enhance diversity and inclusion within their organisations and investments. The reason for doing so goes beyond the basic principles of social justice. Companies that reflect the societies into which they are born and the markets they serve are likely to be more resilient in the longer term.

Developing the Gender & Diversity Index involved a range of activities, from identifying and analysing existing data, identifying data gaps and conducting new research to fill them to engaging with a wide range of stakeholders to prove or disprove our initial hypotheses, investigate causal links and, ultimately, validate findings. In particular, several qualitative

¹ https://eic.ec.europa.eu/index_en

² https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/step-scale_en

³ European Commission: European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, The European Innovation Council – Impact report 2023 – Accelerating Deep Tech in Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/072707>

interviews were conducted to investigate the existing barriers for women founders, co-founders and investors, taking into account their personal and professional backgrounds and how their careers have developed over the years.

The framework will underpin an interactive dashboard and a self-assessment widget (GENDEX Pulse), enabling stakeholders to benchmark and analyse their own performance and identify corrective measures.

The wider objective of GENDEX is to drive systemic change, leading to greater gender diversity and inclusion in the European innovation ecosystem. By highlighting the correlation between diversity and financial performance, as well as broader sustainability, GENDEX aims to provide data points that can drive change toward a fair, competitive, resilient and sustainable Europe.

The key objectives were to:

- Develop a pilot innovation gender & diversity index based on agreed definitions and indicators that can be applied to start-ups/ SMEs and to innovation investment actors in the EU
- Identify relevant sources of reliable and robust data
- Develop methodologies and collect to fill data gaps
- Implement and produce a pilot gender and diversity index using available data from different sources, as well as additional collected data as appropriate
- Make recommendations for the further development and implementation of an innovation gender and diversity index, as well as additional measures needed to improve data availability and benchmarking (e.g., voluntary reporting standards for start-ups, scale-ups and investment funds)
- Disseminate and promote the results of the project to investors, policy-makers and the wider innovation ecosystem

2.3 Key elements of the pilot Gender & Diversity Index

The term diversity encompasses a wide variety of traits and characteristics,⁴ ranging from gender to ethnicity, religion, socioeconomic status and more. The GENDEX pilot focuses on gender as a starting point, while recognising that further work will be needed to shine a light on diversity gaps in the deep tech ecosystem.

Our baseline is the definition of a woman-led company as a company with at least one woman in a key executive or board position, including founders and co-founders⁵. This definition, validated by the GENDEX Board of Experts, acknowledges and makes visible the presence of women in leadership roles in terms of driving the strategic direction of a company. Additionally, the GENDEX Board of Experts noted that board membership is considered an integral and important part of governance. While we at GENDEX recognise that an ideal

⁴ For a fuller review of this point, please refer to D1.1 Report on the State of the Art.

⁵ Some exceptions to this definition were necessary due to data availability constraints in certain cases. Please refer to the Methodology and limitations section.

definition would include women's shareholdings relative to other founders (taking into account dilution), these data are not readily available from current sources. Furthermore, it is common practice in some EU countries to have holding companies and vehicles rather than individual shareholdings, which further complicates the applicability of this ideal definition.

GENDEX's definition of a woman-led company is not the end goal but a starting point, providing a measurable criterion for data collection. While acknowledging that one woman in a leadership role is only a minimum baseline, its foundational definition is essential to building a robust index and driving meaningful change in the deep tech ecosystem. It is the first step on a longer journey.

2.2.1 GENDEX analytical framework

The developed index is aimed at answering the question of why so few women-led companies in deep tech are funded. Specifically, the analysis of results provided in this report are aimed at confirming or disputing the following hypotheses:

1. There is a lack of diversity in the deep tech sectors targeted by the EIC.
2. The lack of diversity at the investment stage stems from a lack of diversity at the earlier stages of the pipeline.
3. Even when investment is secured, women receive term sheets with less favourable terms than those offered to men.
4. The investment gap between women and men highlights an opportunity to expand the pool of deep tech founders.

Where necessary, the report also indicates when a lack of data has made it impossible to prove a given hypothesis definitively.

2.2.2 GENDEX scope

The scope of GENDEX, developed under the funded pilot initiative, focuses on providing the EIC and the broader European innovation ecosystem with actionable insights into diversity within the investment and entrepreneurial landscapes in Europe.

A key aspect of the index is the comparative analysis of companies, founders and investors associated with the deep tech ecosystem targeted by the EIC. However, data collection and availability challenges were encountered during the process. These challenges are discussed in greater detail in the Methodology and limitations section of the report annex. As highlighted at the end of this section, EIC's own data were not analysed in the development of the index.

Therefore, the final scope of GENDEX is:

- Geographical
 - EU27
 - United Kingdom⁶
 - United States/China⁷

⁶ The United Kingdom retains significant relevance for the European investment ecosystem, with significant flows of capital, companies and talent.

⁷ Where relevant, comparisons can be made from provided data sets.

- Tech area – defined by the technologies in scope for the EIC⁸
 - Quantum technologies
 - Robotics and autonomous systems
 - Advanced materials, manufacturing and recycling technologies
 - Space and propulsion technologies
 - Advanced sensing technologies
 - Biotechnologies and medical devices
 - AI technologies
 - Advanced connectivity, navigation and digital technologies
- Funding stage
 - Pre-seed and seed
 - Early VC: Series A to Series B rounds
 - Later VC: Series E to Series D rounds
 - Venture growth: Series E+ to IPO
- Period
 - 2014–2024⁹

The Gender & Diversity Validated Index Scorecard: Results Analysis section presents key insights derived exclusively from the data analysis. As a result, it may not provide detailed perspectives for each of the specific listed in-scope elements. Comprehensive data tables can be found in D3.2: Validated Gender & Diversity Index Scorecard.

****Note:** All data referred to in this report are not EIC's own data. Data analysis is based on a sample of deep tech segments of companies in scope for the EIC, with secondary data collection using company databases (e.g., PitchBook and Dealroom) and, in the case of primary data collection (e.g., the GENDEX survey), including respondents who reported receiving EIC funding, grants, or both¹⁰.

2.2.3 The Gender & Diversity Index outline

The GENDEX index applies a hierarchical view across four tiers that map relationships between indicators both vertically and laterally. An additional women-investor-specific tier has been developed alongside the main framework:

⁸ European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, The European Innovation Council – Impact report 2023 – Accelerating Deep Tech in Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/072707>

⁹ Where possible, we aimed to access data points over a 10-year period, which aligns with the period for measuring the performance of funds and deep tech start-ups, as well as the impact of talent pools and drivers.

¹⁰ Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for other details.

Figure 1. Overview of indicators across all tiers and segments of the index

Source: GENDEX, 2024

Each indicator in **Figure 1** is composed of one or more metrics linked to an individual data source, as listed in **Table 1**:

Table 1. Final list of metrics for the Gender & Diversity Index

#	INDICATOR	METRIC
DEEP TECH TALENT TIER		
DT1	Women with an undergraduate degree in STEM	Number of women chairs researchers in STEM in academia
DT2	Women researchers in STEM	Number of women researchers in STEM in academia
DT3	Women employed in STEM	Number of women employed in R&D in the public and private sector
DT4	Women chairs in STEM subjects at top-tier institutions	Share of women leaders in STEM at top-tier institutions
INTELLECTUAL & SOCIAL CAPITAL TIER		
IS1a	Term sheet differential	Average valuation of women-led companies
IS1b		Vesting schedules at first raise for women founders

IS2	Time to raise first cheque	Difference in time to raise for women-led companies
IS3a	Women-led companies	Share of women-led companies
IS3b		Participation of women across teams
IS4a	Women in deep tech	Share of women employed in top tier tech companies
IS4b		Share of women employed in top-performing research institutions
IS5a	IP held by women	Share of PCTs with a named woman inventor
IS5b		IP ownership of women founders
ASSET & INVESTMENT TIER		
AI1a	Sustained value in women led companies	Difference in burn rates by women-led companies
AI1b		Retention of company valuation by women-led companies
AI1c		Difference in market capitalisation 12 months after IPO for women-led companies
AI2a	Exits of women founders of European companies	Number of IPOs of women-led companies
AI2b		Number of exits by women founders (non-IPO)
AI2c		Valuation of exits by women founders (non-IPO)
AI2d		Valuation on IPO of women-led companies
AI3a	Women-led unicorns	Number of women-led companies valued at over \$1 billion
AI3b		Time to reach unicorn classification
AI4a	Funds raised by women-led companies in Europe	Investment raised by women-led companies
AI4b		Share of investment rounds by women-led companies
INVESTOR TIER		

I1a	Women investors	Share of women GPs in European investment firms with a European entity
I1b		Share of women angel investors
I2a	Diversity in funds	Share of women-led companies funded by funds active in Europe
I2b		AUM in VC funds with at least one woman decision-maker

Source: GENDEX, 2024

The Gender & Diversity Validated Index Scorecards: Results Analysis section provides key insights into the data underlying each indicator, highlighting specific correlations between metrics and tiers where relevant. The analysis follows the investment pipeline, starting with the deep tech talent tier and moving down to the asset and investment tier. As mentioned earlier, the investor tier is treated separately, offering additional insights into gender representation within investment firms, a critical factor in the investment pipeline.

At this stage, given the sensitivity of the topic, GENDEX will not draw definitive conclusions from the statistical analysis on gender diversity and its correlation with superior performance within the impact tier of the European deep tech ecosystem¹¹.

Note: For narrative clarity, the analysis of indicators within each tier may deviate from the Gender & Diversity Index code sequence defined in D1.2 Gender & Diversity Scorecard and the table above.

¹¹ See Annex A: Methodology and limitations for further details.

3 GENDER & DIVERSITY VALIDATED INDEX SCORECARD: RESULTS ANALYSIS

3.1 Deep tech talent tier

Deep tech, driven by cutting-edge engineering and scientific breakthroughs, plays a transformative role in shaping society. Yet the field continues to grapple with a significant challenge: the underrepresentation of women. This disparity is rooted in deep-seated socioeconomic and cultural barriers, including a gender imbalance in STEM education and the prevailing cultural narrative that frames science and technology as predominantly male domains.

A woman deep tech founder who took part in the GENDEX interview series highlighted the cultural dynamics contributing to this gap, stating, *'After high school, women are more encouraged to pursue soft skills rather than tech entrepreneurship.'*¹²

Research has shown one of the most impactful strategies to address the gender gap is to involve girls in STEM education from a young age, fostering their confidence and interest in these fields before societal stereotypes can influence their decisions¹³. Without early positive experiences, girls are less likely to engage in STEM subjects in high school and beyond, particularly in technical fields such as engineering and computer science.

STEM careers are expected to be at the heart of the future job market and provide considerably higher income opportunities. To address the existing disparities in workforce participation, compensation and leadership effectively, it is essential to establish more robust pathways that enable girls and women to advance in STEM education, thus laying the foundation of new women-led deep tech start-ups.

To illustrate the status of gender equality in deep tech throughout Europe, we gathered data across the following four metrics:

- Women graduates in STEM subjects
- Women researchers in STEM in academia
- Women employed in STEM
- Women chairs in STEM subjects at top-tier institutions

DT1 Women graduates in STEM subjects

In 2022, the proportion of women among STEM graduates in the European Union neared gender parity, with women making up 42% of all STEM graduates in the region. However,

¹² All quotes and qualitative insights featured in this report are included in D2.3 Qualitative Interview Results.

¹³ Evagorou, M., Puig, B., Bayram, D. and Janeckova, H. (2024). 'Addressing the gender gap in STEM education across educational levels', NESET report, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. doi: 10.2766/260477

between 2017 and 2022, progress was limited, as the representation of women across all STEM disciplines rose by merely 3%. (Figure 2).

While gender representation among STEM graduates appears to be fairly equal, specific disciplines – such as mathematics (-7%) and physics (-11%) – have witnessed significant decreases in the proportion of female graduates since 2017. Conversely, the number of female graduates in engineering has remained consistent, with a modest increase of 3%. The field of information and communication technology (ICT) has experienced the most pronounced growth in women graduates (+8%). However, despite this growth, the number of women graduates is still low; in 2022, only 25% and 28% of ICT and engineering graduates, respectively, were women. Therefore, it is worth remarking that gender disparity remains pronounced in two of the rapidly expanding deep tech disciplines most closely associated with founding scalable start-ups.

Figure 2. Percentage of women graduates in STEM subjects, 2017 vs. 2022

Source: GENDEX elaboration on Eurostat data; distribution of male and female graduates in different fields of education, by education level and programme orientation [educ_uoe_grad10]; October 2024

Eurostat data can be compared with results from the GENDEX survey, conducted in summer 2024 among a total sample of 150 respondents across European countries and the United Kingdom (51 women respondents, 98 men respondents and one respondent who preferred not to declare their gender). Survey results show engineering (35%) is the most common field of study for entrepreneurs in this field. The gender gap was once again apparent, with exactly 25% of women respondents graduating in this field, compared with 40% of men. Similarly, the share of ICT and computer science graduates is twice as high among men founders (12%) as among women founders (6%)¹⁴.

Analysing the data by country shows France has achieved the most notable increase in female STEM graduates, with a rise of 11%, resulting in a near-equal representation of female graduates at 45%. A possible contributing factor could be the influence of privately funded

¹⁴ See D2.2 Quantitative Survey Results for full banner tables and results.

programmes in the country (e.g., the L'Oréal-UNESCO Young Talents France for Women in Science and the De Vinci Women's Empowerment Scholarship. In contrast, several other countries (including Germany, Spain, Italy, the Benelux nations and those in Scandinavia) report female graduate proportions of around 40%, with only minimal changes observed from 2017 to 2022. Furthermore, Hungary and Cyprus have experienced the most significant declines within the European Union, with 6% fewer women STEM graduates in 2022 than in 2017 (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Percentage of women graduates in STEM subjects by country, 2017 vs. 2022

Source: GENDEX elaboration on Eurostat data, distribution of male and female graduates in different fields of education, by education level and programme orientation [educ_uoe_grad10]; October 2024

Note: Missing country data has resulted in an incomplete representation of the EU27 member states in this chart

DT2 Women researchers in STEM subjects at universities

Moving on to research, the presence of women STEM researchers is essential for generating the IP that forms the basis of a deep tech company.

The GENDEX survey reveals that academia and research are the most common career backgrounds for founders of both genders before starting their own businesses. However, the data show a notable gender disparity: While 60% of men respondents had prior experience in these fields, only 45% of women respondents reported the same.

While several EU countries can show gains in terms of women improving their educational qualifications and representing a nearly equal share of STEM graduates, the gender disparity in STEM degree enrolments still results in a gender gap in the pursuit of a STEM career. Data from the EU clearly shows that in 2022, the percentage of female STEM researchers stood at 31%, reflecting only a marginal increase from the 30% in 2017 (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Percentage of male/female researchers in STEM subjects at universities, 2017 vs. 2022

Source: Eurostat; , R&D personnel by sector of performance, professional position and sex [rd_p_persocc]; October 2024

The data indicate only modest progress in achieving gender balance among STEM researchers, despite extensive policy commitments to promoting gender equality in research. Among European countries, Bulgaria (35%), Latvia (35%) and Lithuania (36%) exhibited the highest proportions of women in STEM research, while Hungary (27%), Luxembourg (26%) and Czechia (26%) ranked the lowest.

At the European level, and in numerous individual countries, a notable trend is that the growth in the total number of women STEM researchers at universities in the 2017-2021 period exceeded that of their men counterparts, with a headcount increase of 13% for women compared with 9% for men. However, even if this growth differential were to be sustained, it would take 19-21 years to achieve gender parity in STEM research (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Headcount growth for STEM researchers by gender, 2017-2022

Source: Eurostat; R&D personnel by sector of performance, professional position and sex [rd_p_persocc]; October 2024

DT3 Women scientists and engineers employed in the public and private sector

The distribution of genders within STEM employment beyond academic environments aligns more closely with the ratio of STEM graduates from universities. In 2022, women represented 41% of the scientist and engineer workforce in both the public and private sector (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Percentage of women scientists and engineers employed in the public and private sector

Source: Eurostat; employed HRST by category, sex, age and NACE Rev. 2 activity [hrst_st_nsecsex2__custom_13050489], October 2024

Note: Missing country data has resulted in an incomplete representation of the EU27 member states in this chart

However, despite ongoing initiatives aimed at fostering growth in science and technology, the data show little change since 2017. In most EU countries, a larger proportion of men continue to occupy these positions. Only Denmark, Lithuania, Bulgaria and Spain report higher or equal representation of women scientists and engineers in their public- and private-sector workforces. Indeed, despite notable advancements since 2017, the most significant gender disparity in employment within these fields can be observed in Hungary (69% male, 31% female) and Finland (68% male, 32% female).

DT4 Women chairs in STEM subjects at top-tier institutions

Despite a gradual rise in the number of women graduates and researchers in STEM fields at universities in the European Union, women remain significantly underrepresented in high-ranking academic roles. As mentioned, women comprised 42% of university STEM graduates in 2022 and represented 31% of STEM researchers. However, only 20–25% of academic leadership positions – such as chairs (i.e., a professor or the leader of a governing body) – in STEM disciplines at prominent universities are occupied by women (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Gender gap pyramid for STEM at EU universities

Sources: Annual D&I reports; institution websites; feedback from university diversity teams; GENDEX estimation

The European gender gap funnel in higher education underscores the persistent scarcity of opportunities for women in STEM disciplines to advance into higher academic positions and, subsequently, into the private sector.

As part of the research into the origins of deep tech companies, we developed a list of leading universities (Figure 8) based on their status as top research institutions in Europe. These institutions are recognised for generating significant spin-out value, as outlined in Dealroom's *European Deep Tech Report 2023*¹⁵. Here, the lack of women in senior STEM research positions can also affect the number of women attracted to research and, consequently, the deep tech talent pool of founders and co-founders.

¹⁵ <https://app.dealroom.co/lists/18527>

Figure 8. Percentage of women chairs in STEM subjects at top-tier European institutions by spin-out value

Sources: Annual D&I reports; institution websites; feedback from university diversity teams; GENDEX estimation

3.2 Intellectual and social capital tier

The intellectual and social capital tier examines the participation and role of women in the business and research communities and shows the societal and intellectual contributions of women in various high-impact fields in the technology and deep tech ecosystems.

Specifically, this tier focuses on:

- **Intellectual property held by women:** Ranging from women founders' general IP ownership compared to that of men to the specific share of PCTs with a woman inventor
- **Women employed in tech and deep tech:** Showcasing the share employed in top-tier tech companies operating in Europe, as well as in top-performing research and technology organizations (RTOs)
- **Women-led deep tech companies:** Exploring the share of women-led companies in the deep tech perimeter of interest and the participation of women across teams
- **Time to raise first cheque:** Understanding the differences in time-to-raise for women-led companies in scope
- **Term sheet differentials:** Analysing the differences in vesting schedules at first raise for women founders and the overall valuations of women-led companies of interest

IS1a Average valuation of women-led companies

Equity financing is the most common type of start-up funding, as it allows them to raise relatively large sums of money without incurring debt but by selling an ownership stake in the company to investors. The average valuation received in this round is a key metric to assess how women-led companies are perceived by investors compared with those led by men. Women-led companies are defined as deep tech companies with at least one woman in a key executive or board position, including founders and co-founders, as opposed to men-led companies, which have an all-men management team and board¹⁶.

¹⁶ Refer to the Glossary of Terms at the start of this report

Figure 9. Average valuation of women-led deep tech companies in first closed investment round (€M)

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000)

Note: Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year

Figure 9 shows the average valuation in the first closed investment round by gender in Europe over a 10-year period. The figure shows statistically relevant samples of companies but is not representative of the entire European landscape due to data availability constraints and inconsistencies in deal reporting, especially at the pre-seed and seed stages.

The average first-round valuation of deep tech companies almost doubled overall in the second half of the 10-year period (2014-2024). This trend applies to both women-led and men-led companies; in both cases, the average valuation increased at a similar rate. This relates to the European funding ecosystem's increasing maturity in terms of the volume of capital raised over the last decade. Nevertheless, the average valuation in the first closed investment round for women-led deep tech start-ups was around 2.4 times lower than for men-led start-ups over the 2014-2024 period.

Figure 10 shows the gaps that exist between EU countries, with Western Europe and the United Kingdom benefiting from a more favourable investment and innovation ecosystem than the rest of the region. This has a knock-on effect, as women raise less when less money is injected into the investment ecosystem.

The qualitative interviews GENDEX conducted for this project indicate that women founders need to develop certain skills (e.g., negotiating techniques) to succeed; they also point to unconscious biases on the side of investors, potentially negatively impacting outcomes for women founders.

These considerations are confirmed by the following analysis of other indicators related to the gender gap in the investment pipeline.

Figure 10. Average valuation of women-led deep tech companies in first closed investment rounds by country, 2024 (average €M)

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000)

Notes: Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year. Where countries are not represented in these figures, the average valuation of women-led deep tech companies in the first closed investment round in that country equals 0.

IS2 Difference in time to raise for women-led companies

Early-stage start-ups rely on external investment to fund daily operations. However, the timing of when founders transition from bootstrapping to seeking outside investors varies across companies and individuals. This indicator is based on data from the GENDEX survey, conducted on a sample of 150 women and men founders in the deep tech sectors in scope for the EIC¹⁷.

As highlighted in D2.3 GENDEX Qualitative Interview Results, women founders tend to approach fundraising with greater caution, prioritising detailed and well-structured investment plans. One founder explained, *'I said I'm not going to take money for this company*

¹⁷ Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for further details on the primary research activities conducted by GENDEX.

until I'm able to stand toe to toe with an investor and really understand the value they add to what I'm doing.'

This cautious approach appears to stem from two key factors. First, anecdotal evidence suggests that women tend to be more risk-averse, preferring to have every aspect of their business in order before pursuing investment opportunities. Second, a widely acknowledged gender bias exists in the technology and investment sectors, leading women founders to ensure they are in the strongest possible position before engaging with investors. Another founder emphasised this strategy, advising, *'Be careful to build your own product first and get customers or at least achieve product-market fit before sitting at the investor table.'*

This mindset significantly impacts the key metric analysed in this section: the time to raise for women-led start-ups. For this study, time to raise is defined as the number of months it takes for a women-led company to secure its first investment cheque compared with men-led start-ups, measured from the company's launch date.

Figure 11. Difference in time to raise for women founders and men founders

GENDEX survey question: How long did it take you to receive your first term sheet?

Source: GENDEX Survey, August 2024 (n = 51), women founders in the EU and UK; (n = 98), men founders in the EU and UK

Figure 11 presents the GENDEX survey results comparing the declared fundraising timelines of women and men founders. The data show that men founders secure the first investment round for their company more quickly, with over 50% of start-ups raising funds within the first six months. In contrast, only 31% of women-led companies receive their first cheque within this timeframe, although 72% raise it within a year. Notably, 28% of deep tech start-ups founded by women take over a year to raise their first round, compared with 9% of men.

On average, it takes women-led companies over 12 months to raise their first cheque, compared with less than six months for men-led companies. A key factor in this difference is the disparity in access to networks and personal connections. As highlighted in D2.3 GENDEX Qualitative Interview Report, women face limited networking opportunities and reduced ecosystem access due to the gender discrepancy within the male-dominated VC landscape.

A 2020 study from the Harvard Business School¹⁸ further supports this, showing that even when women are exposed to the same VC networking opportunities, they are less likely to reach out to VCs and other investors they already know. This reluctance stems from differences in networking norms, the tendency for networks to favour individuals with similar backgrounds (*homophily*), and concerns about potential bias, discrimination or harassment.

As noted in the GENDEX interviews, the exclusivity of accelerators and VC firms often drives women founders to seek other professional networks (e.g., professional associations, early customers, national agencies or business associations) to support their business development. While effective, these alternative routes can also extend the time to raise external funds, leading to prolonged bootstrapping. These structural barriers, together with the more cautious approach women founders tend to take in investment pitches, further widens the disparity in the start-up ecosystem.

IS1b Vesting schedules at first raise for women founders

Vesting schedules serve as a key indicator in evaluating whether women founders are treated differently from their male counterparts. The vesting period refers to the period over which an equity owner gradually earns the right to exercise their options, while the cliff represents the initial period during which no options are vested.

The most common option is a four-year vesting schedule with a one-year cliff, indicated by 46% of men founders and 29% of women founders. This structure provides the founder with an incentive to continue contributing to the company's development and strategic direction for a longer period. However, the majority of women respondents (33%) preferred not to answer this question. A further 20% of women founders were in the process of negotiating their first deal, were too early to raise or had signed less favourable deals (compared with 4% of men founders).

Overall, 28% of men founders had signed on more favourable terms that stipulated a three-year vesting schedule with a six-month cliff, compared with only 12% of women founders. In comparison, the results for a subsample of 75 EIC recipients showed even starker differences, with only 6% of women founders having a three-year vesting agreement, compared with 23% of men, and 34% preferring not to answer.

What conclusions can be drawn from these trends? As pointed out by the GENDEX Board of Experts, this highlights a potential lack of negotiating power among women founders. (Un)conscious biases could influence how investors perceive and interact with women founders during negotiations, potentially leading to less favourable outcomes for women. This hypothesis has been confirmed through the qualitative interviews GENDEX conducted with women founders.

Figure 12 shows the most common vesting schedules agreed upon by equity holders at the time of the first deal, along with the corresponding proportions of women and men founders and co-founders, as reported in the GENDEX survey¹⁹.

¹⁸ https://www.hbs.edu/ris/Publication%20Files/19-105_eba8b116-90b6-41c0-b02e-888746116201.pdf

¹⁹ As mentioned above, for the indicators based on the results of the GENDEX survey, we refer to men and women founders and co-founders and not specifically to the GENDEX definition of women-led companies. Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for more details.

The most common option is a four-year vesting schedule with a one-year cliff, indicated by 46% of men founders and 29% of women founders. This structure provides the founder with an incentive to continue contributing to the company’s development and strategic direction for a longer period. However, the majority of women respondents (33%) preferred not to answer this question. A further 20% of women founders were in the process of negotiating their first deal, were too early to raise or had signed less favourable deals (compared with 4% of men founders).

Overall, 28% of men founders had signed on more favourable terms that stipulated a three-year vesting schedule with a six-month cliff, compared with only 12% of women founders. In comparison, the results for a subsample of 75 EIC recipients showed even starker differences, with only 6% of women founders having a three-year vesting agreement, compared with 23% of men, and 34% preferring not to answer.

What conclusions can be drawn from these trends? As pointed out by the GENDEX Board of Experts, this highlights a potential lack of negotiating power among women founders. (Un)conscious biases could influence how investors perceive and interact with women founders during negotiations, potentially leading to less favourable outcomes for women. This hypothesis has been confirmed through the qualitative interviews GENDEX conducted with women founders.

Figure 12. Vesting schedules at first raise – women founders vs. men founders

GENDEX survey question: How long was your vesting schedule in your first raise?

Source: GENDEX Survey, August 2024 (n = 51), women founders in the EU and UK; (n = 98), men founders in the EU and UK

The majority of interviewed women deep tech founders reported being treated differently than their men counterparts when sitting at the investor table. Being less listened to when speaking about technical aspects is commonly reported. One interviewee stated, *'What I think is that there is no ... obvious or explicit downgrading or ignoring because I'm a woman. There is a lot of ... unconscious bias' around women being less capable than men in scientific subjects. This leads women founders to 'build additional knowledge around effective influencing as a woman, knowing how to have a seat at the table'. A common sentiment among interviewees was, 'Sometimes women keep a low profile and are perceived as not being bold enough [by investors].'*

Age and experience, for both men and women, impact their ability to negotiate with investors and speak the 'investors' language', a point that was emphasised by the interviewed women founders. However, mentors, advisors and policymakers could provide improved access to information and resources on best practices in negotiating and structuring vesting schedules to help women founders in their first fundraising.

IS3a Share of women-led companies

The indicator measuring women-led companies references the share of deep tech companies with at least one woman in a key executive or board position (including founders and co-founders), as opposed to men-led companies, with an all-men management and board.

Figure 13. Share of women-led companies in deep tech by country, 2014 vs. 2024

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000); GENDEX analysis of a sample of US companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 38,000); GENDEX analysis of a sample of Chinese companies (N ≈ 12,850)

While some overall advances have been made in the number of women in leadership positions in most EU countries and the UK, the share of deep tech companies with at least one woman in a key executive or board position (as defined and measured by GENDEX) remains low. **Figure 13** shows the overall EU and UK average moved up two percentage points in the 2014-2024 period, reaching 22%. On average, 22% of deep tech companies are women-led. In 2024, Sweden, Estonia, Ireland, Romania and Spain were the best-performing European countries in terms of this indicator. Romania, Bulgaria and Luxembourg had the most positive relative change over this period.

Comparing the results for the EU27 and the United Kingdom with the average shares for the United States and China shows a significant difference in both cases. In the United States, the average share was around 39% in both 2014 and 2024, with no significant change over the ten-year period. However, this higher share could be related to a larger, more mature venture capital ecosystem with greater overall availability of funding for start-ups, including those led by women. Additionally, various initiatives and policies in the US (e.g., grants and funding programs) are designed to support women in tech. These include the Women's Global Trade Empowerment Program from the International Trade Administration and the Women's Entrepreneurship (WE) program from the U.S. Trademark and Patent Office²⁰.

In contrast, the share of women-led companies in China remains at 10%, with no significant increase in the last 10 years. Despite women making up nearly half of China's science and technology workforce, they hold only a small fraction (6%) of memberships in the Chinese Academy of Sciences, reflecting a significant gender imbalance in STEM research. To address this, the government has committed to increasing gender equity through initiatives such as enhanced training, career development programs and recruiting more women for leadership roles²¹. Confucian values and traditional gender roles often strongly emphasise women's roles within the family and as caregivers. For instance, research²² shows that Confucianism is significantly negatively associated with board gender diversity, suggesting the proportion of women directors in the boardroom is significantly lower for firms with a strong atmosphere of Confucianism.

²⁰ <https://www.commerce.gov/work-us/services-businesses/resources-women-entrepreneurs#:~:text=The%20Women's%20Global%20Trade%20Empowerment,wish%20to%20boldly%20grow%20their>

²¹ <https://www.china-briefing.com/news/china-takes-steps-to-empower-women-latest-developments-in-womens-protection-law/>

²² Du, Xingqiang. (2014). Does Confucianism Reduce Board Gender Diversity? Firm-Level Evidence from China. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 136. 10.1007/s10551-014-2508-x.

Figure 14. Share of women-led companies in European deep tech by technology area, 2014 vs. 2024 (%)

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000)

Note: Companies may belong to multiple segments, which may result in double counting. Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year

Figure 14 shows that in terms of European deep tech technology areas, biotechnologies, robotics and autonomous systems and quantum technologies currently have the highest share of women-led companies.

IS3b Participation of women across teams

Research shows a strong business case for diverse leadership teams – both boards and executive teams²³. McKinsey’s Diversity Matters report series, spanning nearly a decade (2015, 2018, 2020 and 2023), demonstrates that the business case for gender diversity on executive teams has more than doubled over the period (measured by the increased likelihood of peer financial outperformance of those companies, demonstrating a steady increase in the representation of women in leadership teams). The link between diverse leadership and higher holistic-impact scores, including environmental and social measures, is also statistically significant.

The Bloomberg Gender-Equality Index 2023²⁴ shows the representation of women on boards is an indicator of the representation of women in senior leadership roles and throughout the

²³ McKinsey & Company, Diversity Matters Even More: The Case for Holistic Impact, November 2023: <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/diversity-and-inclusion/diversity-matters-even-more-the-case-for-holistic-impact#/>

²⁴ https://assets.bbhub.io/company/sites/51/2023/02/2178700_BBGT_ESG_2023-GEI-Global-Campaign_BCH_230124-1-1.pdf

organisation. It also suggests that a higher concentration of women in senior management roles influences a company’s ability to attract, retain and develop women for senior leadership positions.

Figure 15. Participation of women across teams by founder's declared gender, 2024

GENDEX survey question: Please estimate each of the following percentages at your company using the ranges provided:

Source: GENDEX Survey, August 2024 (n = 51), women founders in the EU and UK; (n = 98), men founders in the EU and UK

Figure 15 presents the survey results on workforce diversity in companies led by European founders. Men respondents said women were consistently underrepresented across all employee categories in their companies²⁵. This gender gap is most pronounced at the board and executive levels, where leadership plays a crucial role in strategic decision-making and governance. In terms of leadership, 42% of women founders report that their executive teams comprise more than 50% women, compared with only 2% of men founders. Similarly, 32% confirmed that more than 50% of their company’s board members are women, compared with 0% for men respondents. This disparity extends to technical roles: 29% of women respondents said more than 50% of those in technical positions at their companies are women, compared with just 1% of men founders.

These findings highlight the significant influence of founder gender on workforce composition and leadership diversity within start-ups.

²⁵ As mentioned above, for the indicators based on the results of the GENDEX survey, we refer to men and women founders and co-founders and not specifically to the GENDEX definition of women-led companies. Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for more details.

Figure 16. Participation of women across teams by EIC beneficiaries and non EIC beneficiaries, 2024

GENDEX survey question: Please estimate each of the following percentages at your company using the ranges provided:

Source: GENDEX Survey, August 2024 (n = 76), founders in the EU and UK who received direct investments, grants and/or equity from the EIC; (n = 74), founders in the EU and UK who were not EIC beneficiaries

Analysing the data (see Figure 16) from the perspective of EIC and non-EIC beneficiaries shows the former tend to have a higher portion of women as executives²⁶. The chart showing the share of women in the total workforce indicates that EIC beneficiaries focus more strongly on diverse hiring than the non-EIC cohort. While gender balance is indeed a consideration in the EIC selection process, it is important to note that due to statistical limitations, these findings highlight a trend rather than providing a fully representative picture of the entire EIC ecosystem.

IS4a Share of women employed in top-tier tech companies

The share of women employed in top-tier tech companies is a critical bellwether for predicting gender diversity in the European deep tech ecosystem. These companies tend to act as hotbeds of technology talent, providing employees with skills, resources and networks that can be carried over to new ventures.

²⁶ Respondents stating that they have received direct investments, grants and/or equity from the EIC in the GENDEX survey. These data are not EIC data

Figure 17. Share of women employed in top-tier European tech companies by 2024 market capitalization (%)

Sources: Annual company reports for SAP, SE, NXP, 3DX, BAE Systems, Infineon and Thales; GENDEX estimations based on a sample of at least 1,000 European employees' profiles on LinkedIn for the other companies

Figure 17 shows the share of women employed by the top 10 largest technology companies (by 2024 market capitalisation) headquartered in Europe. Those in the services sectors appear to be more successful in attracting and/or retaining women than those in more industrial sectors.

A similar situation applies to the Magnificent 7 (Figure 18). However, it is important to note that not all companies in this group publicly disclose regional diversity data. As a result, estimates had to be made for Europe, which may affect accuracy. In general, technology companies with a significant focus on advisory/consulting and services, or those with a large salesforce organisation, tend to have a larger proportion of women in their workforce than pure hardware or software companies.

Figure 18. Share of women employed in top-tier tech companies - Magnificent 7 (%)

Sources: Microsoft annual company report; GENDEX estimations based on Amazon annual company report; GENDEX estimations based a sample of at least 1,000 European employees' profiles on LinkedIn for the other companies

Figure 19 focuses on gender diversity in top European tech unicorns²⁷. Three out of nine tech unicorns boast relatively high rates of women employees (above 35%).

The defence technology company Helsing or the large language model provider Mistral AI (both in the field of artificial intelligence and machine learning) have a lower proportion of female employees, according to GENDEX's analysis. The difference with companies such as Personio, ContentSquare or Mirakl (which operate in the HR tech, customer experience and online marketplace sectors, respectively) can be attributed to a higher concentration of engineering and research roles in Helsing and MistralAI. As described above, gender imbalances are strongest among engineering and ICT graduates.

Figure 19. Share of women employed in top-tier tech companies - top European tech unicorns and former unicorns (%)

Sources: Top European tech unicorns were selected based on the last available post-valuation; Relex annual company report; GENDEX estimations based on a sample of at least 1,000 European employees' profiles on LinkedIn for the other companies. The companies are ranked by the highest share (%) of women employed.

IS4b Share of women employed in top-performing research institutions

This indicator measures women's participation in top-performing European RTOs and institutions on the basis that these environments are conducive to IP generation. Previous research by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation²⁸ showed that efforts to implement measures of institutional change for gender equality in research organisations in the EU had been successful. In 2020, most of these organisations across EU member states and associated countries took actions and measures to achieve gender equality (i.e., developed strategies and policies, set goals and implemented monitoring and reporting systems). This could be attributed to the EU's 2019 Gender Equality Strategy, which made gender equality and inclusiveness in the European Research Area (ERA) a priority in terms of both strategy and funding.

²⁷ Check key definitions in Annex A, Methodology and limitations, for a definition of 'unicorn'.

²⁸ She Figures 2021, EC

Figure 20. Share of women employed in top-performing research institutions, 2023 (%)

Sources: Research institutions' D&I annual reports, ranking by the highest production of patents within the 2014-2024 period, according to the number of patent filings in the PATSTAT database

Figure 20 shows the gender diversity numbers for the top-performing research institutions in the EU and UK. These research institutions were ranked by the number of patents awarded in the 2014-2024 period²⁹. In 2023, the average proportion of women working at these institutions was 38%, a proportion that varies between 59% at the Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale (France) and 24% at Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Angewandten Forschung (Germany).

²⁹ Refer to the Methodology and limitations section of this report for further details.

IS5a Share of PCTs with a named woman inventor

Historically, women have been underrepresented amongst patent inventors.³⁰ However, patents play a key role in the success of deep tech start-ups, providing legal protection for R&D results and recognising intellectual property rights. For this indicator, patent applications available through the European Patent Office (EPO) database (PATSTAT) were analysed for the 2014-2024 period, with gender being inferred by inventor name and the results being filtered for those residing in a European country³¹.

Figure 21. Share of patents with a named woman inventor in selected European countries, 2014-2024 (%)

Source: GENDEX analysis of 132,384 PCT applications (2014-2024) registered in the PATSTAT database, October 2024

On average, over the 2014-2024 period, 24% of inventor teams (patent teams) had a named woman as a team member. Worryingly, Figure 21 indicates that the average rate for women participation in inventor teams declined during the period, from 24% in 2014 to 21% in 2024. Among the largest European economies, Spain and Italy had the highest share of women participating in inventor teams (35% and 28%, respectively) of all inventors in 2024, closely followed by France (26% of all inventors).

These data are in line with a similar analysis carried out by the EPO in a study on women's participation in inventive activity, in which the latest data showed that 27% of all the patent applications filed at the EPO by European applicants in 2023 named at least one woman as an

³⁰ IPO, Gender profiles in worldwide patenting An analysis of female inventorship (2019 edition) (October 2, 2019). Intellectual Property Office Research Paper, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4101200> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4101200>

³¹ Refer to the Methodology and limitations section of this report for further details.

inventor³². Slight discrepancies in the two analyses may be due to different results in inferring names from gender, which (although subject to error) is currently the only approach for proxying women inventorship. Recent research by SheFigures shows that the proportion of women inventors is even lower when calculated based on the number of patent applications and the corresponding number of inventors, with women accounting for only 9% of inventors in the EU³³.

Figure 22. Share of patents with a named woman inventor by International Patents Classification, 2014-2024 (%)

Source: GENDEX analysis of 132,384 PCT applications (2014-2024) registered in the PATSTAT database, October 2024

Patent applications span many different technology subclasses; they are classified into one or more of these subclasses in accordance with the International Patent Classification (IPC)³⁴. This classification is available from the PATSTAT data set. According to GENDEX's analysis, chemistry stands out as the sector with the highest share of women inventors over the 2014-2024 period, with approximately four times the number of women inventors in mechanical engineering. Chemistry also shows the strongest growth over the selected period.

³² Women's participation in inventive activity. Evidence from EPO data, November 2022. https://link.epo.org/web/womens_participation_in_inventive_activity_2022_en.pdf and <https://www.epo.org/en/about-us/statistics/patent-index-2023/statistics-and-indicators/applicants/women-inventors#:~:text=In%20November%202022%2C%20the%20EPO,were%20named%20as%20inventors%20on>

³³ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *She figures 2024 - Infographic*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2025, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/325388>

³⁴ <https://www.wipo.int/en/web/classification-ipc>

IS5b IP ownership of women founders

As mentioned, women tend to be significantly underrepresented amongst IP professionals.³⁵ The data from the underlying research shows that positive action by organizations can reverse the trend.

Data for this indicator were collected through the GENDEX survey.³⁶

Figure 23. IP ownership of women founders by gender, 2024

GENDEX survey question: Which of the following intellectual property (IP) types do you personally own? [Choose all that apply] (%):

Source: GENDEX Survey, August 2024 (n = 51), women founders in the EU and UK; (n = 98), men founders in the EU and UK

The survey data show gender differences in the type of IP that is protected. The biggest of these differences relates to the registration of patents and trademarks, which 80% and 73% of men respondents, respectively, claim to own, compared with 57% and 51% of women. However, when it comes to copyright, there is a higher proportion of women founders: 29% compared with 20% of men. The data also reveal a gap in non-personally owned IP: 10% for women vs. 3% for men.

Similarly, other GENDEX survey results also show that women founders are less likely to bring IP from previous companies or from a research institution. This may also influence the lower spin-off activity of women founders, with just under 30% of women respondents having developed their IP independently. There are concerning anecdotes, confirmed by one of the women interviews, of IP theft in academic environments where more senior researchers claim the inventions.

³⁵ Diversity in the European Innovation Industry and IP Profession, IPOA, March 2022

³⁶ As mentioned above, for the indicators based on the results of the GENDEX survey, we refer to men and women founders and co-founders and not specifically to the GENDEX definition of women-led companies. Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for more details.

3.3 Asset and investment tier

The asset and investment tier focuses on presenting data on the systemic gap in investment raised and value generated by women-led companies. Specifically, this tier focuses on:

- **Sustained value in women-led companies:** Looking at indicators such as the difference in median burn rates for women-led companies compared with those led by men. It also considers the retention of company valuation by women-led companies, looking at the share of down rounds over the total number of deals in the European market, as well as the difference in market capitalisation 12 months after IPO.
- **Exits of women founders of European companies:** Analysing the number and total value of IPO and non-IPO exits (mergers, acquisitions and buy-outs) by women founders.
- **Women-led unicorns:** Identifying the number of women-led private companies in EU member states and the UK with a valuation above \$1 billion and determining the median time to unicorn status.
- **Funds raised by women-led companies in Europe:** Focusing on the total number of deals and investments raised by women-led deep tech companies, again compared with those led by men.

AI1a Difference in burn rates in women-led companies

The monthly burn rate³⁷ is a key financial performance indicator for start-ups and investors. Deep tech start-ups often require significant upfront investment and may take years to generate revenue, often sustaining themselves largely on the capital raised, especially in the early stages. Burn rates help companies and investors understand the company's runway, (i.e., the time until the money runs out), the amount of funding needed for each stage of development and the timing of future fundraising rounds. A higher burn rate indicates a company is spending its cash reserves more quickly.

Figure 24 Median burn rates for women-led and men-led companies, 2014–2023 (€M)

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000)

³⁷ The monthly burn rate can be defined as the amount of money a company spends each month, typically expressed as a negative cash flow. For start-ups and scale-ups, cash reserves usually coincide with capital raised from investors.

Note: Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year.

Figure 25 shows the trend in the median burn rate of women-led companies and the median burn rate of all-men teams in the total EU27 and UK deep tech sample in scope from 2014 to 2023. The burn rate was calculated as the capital raised by women-led and men-led companies in a given round, divided by the number of months until the next round. The year 2024 was not included in the analysis for this metric, as the small number of deals found, especially for women-led companies, would result in outliers that affect the median calculation; furthermore, data collection only covers the first 10 months of the year.

Higher burn rates indicate that in that specific year, women-led companies were spending their cash reserves more quickly³⁸. Women-led companies outperformed men-led companies in five out of the nine years over the given period.

As noted, the data show that women-led companies receive less funding than their men-led counterparts. Smaller rounds imply a shorter period before having to raise more capital. This can lead to more conservative spending and potentially lower burn rates in a company’s early stages.

Figure 25. Difference in median burn rates in women-led companies and men-led companies by stage, 2014-2023 (€M)

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000)

Note: Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year

Looking at the median difference in burn rate by stage between women-led and men-led companies (the median burn rate for women-led companies minus the median burn-rate for men-led companies for each year), the available data show that women-led companies have consistently outperformed those led by men in the pre-seed and seed stages in the given period (Figure 25). This could be related to the fact that women-led companies tend to face more difficulties in fundraising, especially in the first round, as shown in this report. In the pre-

³⁸ Small changes in column heights for the same value in the graph are due to rounding.

seed and seed stages, women-led companies may prefer to optimise their expenditure due to the lower amount of capital raised. At later stages, men-led companies outperform those led by women.

In this case, women-led companies might prioritise sustainable long-term growth over rapid expansion. This could mean investing more in areas such as research and development and customer acquisition, potentially leading to higher burn rates in growth phases.

However, as highlighted by the GENDEX Board of Experts, the individual experience of the founders and management team can sometimes be more influential than gender in burn rate performance. It is important to note this is a nuanced issue, and one which continues to be researched and debated.

Allb Retention of company valuation by women-led companies

In the venture capital and start-up world, a 'down round' is a round of funding in which a company raises money at a lower valuation than in the previous round. Down rounds can signal that a company is facing challenges (e.g., slower-than-expected growth, increased competition or unforeseen obstacles). Comparing the share of women-led and male-led down rounds out of the total number of rounds for deep tech companies of size in the 27 EU member states and the UK over a 10-year period shows that the average share in both cases is 9% (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Share of down rounds for women-led companies vs. all-men-led companies in the EU27 and UK, 2014–2024 (%)

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000)

Note: Note: Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year

Initial fundraising challenges can lead to fewer women-led companies raising, with those that do, raising less capital than male-led companies; however, the data show no significant difference between men- and women-led companies in down rounds. This trend is confirmed by country-specific analyses of countries with a more mature investment environment (e.g., the UK, France and Germany). For countries with a less developed funding ecosystem, outliers may skew the trend, making it more difficult to draw correlations in the data set.

However, in 2023, when VC investment contracted, the share of down rounds for women-led companies was slightly higher: 14% vs. 12% for men-led companies. Competition for limited funding intensified, and women-led companies could have been more prone to accepting less favourable terms to raise capital.

Other interannual differences (e.g., between 2016 and 2017) do not appear to be gender-related, as both years saw a surge in investment landscape activity.

AI2a Number of IPOs for women-led companies

The standard exit strategy for deep tech companies is not to go public but to be acquired, as highlighted by the GENDEX expert panels (non-IPO exits are analysed in indicators AI2b and AI2c).

Figure 27 shows the total annual number of IPOs for companies with women founders and companies with only men founders in the EU27 and UK in the 2014-2024 period³⁹.

Figure 27. Number of IPOs for women and men founders and total sum between 2014 and 2024

Source: GENDEX analysis of a Dealroom sample (N = 150) of EU and UK companies that underwent an IPO

As with other investment-related metrics, the graph clearly shows the difference between the total number of IPOs led by women and those led by men, which are just over 8% of the total number of IPOs over the period. The sum of men-led IPOs is 10 times larger than the sum of women-led IPOs (Figure 28).

³⁹ For indicators based only on the Dealroom data set - IPOs and non-IPO exits and unicorns - the standard GENDEX definition of a woman-led company is not applicable due to data availability constraints. For these indicators, the analysis is performed by comparing companies with at least one woman founder/co-founder with founding teams composed only of men. Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for further details.

Figure 28. Performance of women-led companies on IPO

Source: GENDEX analysis of a Dealroom sample (N = 150) of EU and UK companies that underwent an IPO

The underfunding of women-led companies hinders their growth and ability to scale, making it harder to reach the stage required for an IPO. For example, in the sample considered for this analysis, only five companies with women founders (38% of the total sample of women-founded companies) reached the venture growth stage (Series E or higher), compared with 82 for companies with only men founders (60% of the total men-only founding team sample). By Series C, D or E, a company has typically demonstrated significant revenue growth, market traction and a clear path to profitability. This makes them more attractive to public investors. Companies that have gone through multiple rounds of funding are also generally better prepared for the financial reporting and compliance requirements of going public.

General investment market conditions also affect the number of IPOs. According to the Dealroom data featured in Atomico's State of European Tech, 2021⁴⁰, 2021 saw the highest number of IPOs recorded in the last five years, and it is currently considered a record-breaking year for venture capital investments in Europe, with just over than \$100 billion invested. Investor confidence was high in 2021, with low interest rates and a strong economic recovery after the initial impact of the COVID-19 pandemic creating a favourable investment environment. This increased investment also resulted in the highest number of women-led IPOs in the sample, although still significantly less than the total number of men-led IPOs in the same year. In 2022, the IPO window closed and the number of IPOs in the sample halved for both categories. As noted above, a negative macroeconomic scenario puts women-led businesses at an even greater disadvantage.

As pointed out by the GENDEX expert panel, It should be noted that apart from gender representation in management and founding teams, IPOs in the US tend to have higher valuations on average than those in Europe. A minority of companies in the sample analysed for this indicator carried out IPOs in the United States. One example is Exscientia, an AI-driven pharmatech company that went public on the Nasdaq under the ticker symbol EXAI in October 2021. The company raised approximately \$350.4 million through its IPO by selling 15,927,500 American depositary shares (ADSs) at \$22.00 per ADS, achieving a valuation of

⁴⁰ Source: Atomico's State of European Tech, 2021: <https://2021.stateofeuropeantech.com/chapter/executive-summary/>

approximately \$2.9 billion⁴¹. Thus, the geography of IPOs may partially distort the analysis of women-led vs. male-led IPOs, although GENDEX estimates this number to be less than 10% of the sample under consideration.

AI1c Difference in market capitalisation 12 months after IPO for women-led companies

As mentioned in metric AI2a, the number of deep tech companies with IPOs is relatively small. Deep tech often requires years of intensive research and development before significant revenues are generated. This can make it difficult to meet the short-term revenue expectations public markets often have.

Nevertheless, the market capitalisation of a company 12 months after its IPO⁴² serves as a crucial performance indicator. It validates the initial valuation, providing a critical signal about the company's success. A significant increase demonstrates the company is meeting or exceeding expectations, attracting further investment and boosting investor confidence. This, in turn, fuels future growth by enabling the company to expand operations and pursue strategic initiatives. Conversely, a decline in market capitalisation signals potential challenges (e.g., underperformance, an overvalued initial valuation or unfavourable market conditions). This can erode investor confidence, hinder future funding opportunities and, ultimately, impact the company's long-term success. This indicator analyses the median of the difference between market capitalisation 12 months after IPO and company valuation at IPO.

However, analysing this indicator by gender in deep tech companies is challenging for different reasons. The number of IPOs for women-led companies is significantly lower than for men-led companies; in both cases, the total number is low in the deep tech segment areas in scope. Some years are not comparable, as there were no IPOs for women-led companies. There are also outliers where the median is equal to the average due to low numbers.

Data for this metric are provided in D3.2 Validated Gender & Diversity Index Scorecard for reference only, but low data availability does not allow significant conclusions to be drawn.

AI2d Valuation on IPO of women-led companies (€M)

This indicator analyses the total value (€M) of IPOs in the reference sample from 2014 to 2024. The significantly lower number of IPOs in the sample for companies with women founders also affects the total amount of capital raised through IPOs (**Figure 29**)⁴³.

⁴¹ <https://investors.exscientia.ai/press-releases/press-release-details/2021/Exscientia-Announces-Closing-of-510.4-Million-Aggregate-Financing-Consisting-of-350.4-Million-Upsized-Initial-Public-Offering-With-Full-Exercise-of-Underwriters-Option-to-Purchase-Additional-ADSs-and-160.0-Million-Concurrent-Private-Placement/default.aspx>

⁴² For a definition of IPO and more details on the number and value of IPOs for deep tech companies, see indicators AI2a and AI2d.

⁴³ For indicators based only on the Dealroom data set - IPOs and non-IPO exits and unicorns - the standard GENDEX definition of a woman-led company is not applicable due to data availability constraints. For these indicators, the analysis is performed by comparing companies with at least one woman founder/co-founder with founding teams composed only of men. Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for further details.

Figure 29. Valuation of IPOs by women founders (€M) and total sum, 2014–2024

Source: GENDEX analysis of a Dealroom sample (N = 150) of EU and UK companies that underwent an IPO

Over the 10-year period, the sum raised by companies with women founders amounted to €11.659 million, while companies with men founders only raised eight times this amount over the same period (€91.853 million). The average amount raised per IPO is €896.86 million for women led companies and €670.46 million for men led companies.

Figure 30. Performance of women-led companies in IPO valuation – full period analysis

Source: GENDEX analysis of a Dealroom sample (N = 150) of EU and UK companies that underwent an IPO

Some differences in the sample should be noted: While the IPOs of men-led companies are well distributed across all deep tech sectors in scope, the IPOs of women-led companies are mainly concentrated in the advanced connectivity and digital technologies and AI/ML sectors. At the same time, the GENDEX interviews reveal a perception that mixed boards and founding teams perform better, as they benefit from a greater variety of inputs and skills.

In terms of country breakdowns, the highest IPO valuations by year for both women and men were recorded in the United Kingdom, with a record amount of over €6 billion in 2021 for companies with at least one woman founder and over €68 billion in 2023 for men founders only. For women founders in particular, Germany ranks second. Together, they represent two of the largest European funding ecosystems. Despite similar trends, Sweden, the Netherlands

and Finland also have high total valuations at IPO for men-led companies in this period. All these countries have well-developed ecosystems, highlighting that proximity to funding is key for a company's growth and fundraising, leading to successful exits.

AI2b Number of exits by women founders (non-IPO)

Deep tech start-ups in certain fields are increasingly leveraging AI as a critical process enabler, allowing them to achieve massive valuations and secure significant investment in a shorter timeframe. As a result, some companies strategically delay IPOs, waiting for the optimal moment to go public (as covered in the previous index), or pursue high-value acquisitions and lucrative partnerships with major technology players.

Serial entrepreneurs build multiple ventures over their careers, often pursuing strategic exits to capitalize on new opportunities. Non-IPO exits (e.g., mergers, acquisitions or buyouts⁴⁴) are more common than IPOs, particularly in the technology and deep tech sectors.

In recent years, the rise of AI and generative AI has further fuelled this trend, with numerous start-ups and scale-ups being swiftly acquired by larger tech firms. Notable examples include Microsoft's acquisition of Inflection AI⁴⁵ in the US and Density's acquisition of Prevision.io⁴⁶ in Europe.

How do exit strategies differ between men-led and women-led companies⁴⁷? This section analyses gender disparities in non-IPO exits, using a key metric that tracks the number of exits by women founders in the deep tech sector via acquisitions, mergers and buy-outs. To provide a meaningful comparison, equivalent data on men-led exits are also included.

This metric is based on data provided by Dealroom on over 1,000 deep tech start-ups and scale-ups between 2014 and October 2024. For this analysis, non-IPO exits are defined as mergers, acquisitions or buy-outs.

Before examining the data, it is worth noting that the lower number of women-led deep tech companies has a logical corresponding impact on the number of exits. This mirrors the trend observed in IPO exits, where the smaller representation of women founders results in fewer non-IPO exits than their male counterparts.

Figure 31. Number of exits (non-IPO) and share of women-led exits for women-led and men-led companies by year, 2014 and 2024

⁴⁴ Buy-out refers to an operation where an investment founder or a company acquires the majority of the company, changing the organizational structure, with the objective of leading the organization. The original founders are either removed from the company leadership or are sidelined by the new management.

⁴⁵ <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/tech/technology/microsofts-650-million-deal-with-inflection-ai-key-things-to-know/articleshow/108699958.cms?from=mdr>

⁴⁶ <https://www.density.io/resources/acquiring-prevision-emea-expansion>

⁴⁷ For indicators based only on the Dealroom data set - IPOs and non-IPO exits and unicorns - the standard GENDEX definition of a woman-led company is not applicable due to data availability constraints. For these indicators, the analysis is performed by comparing companies with at least one woman founder/co-founder with founding teams composed only of men. Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for further details.

Source: GENDEX analysis of a Dealroom sample (N = 1,300) of EU and UK companies acquired, merged and/or bought out

Figure 31 shows the relative non-IPO exits for men- and women-led companies for the 2014-2024 period, with 77 exits for women-led companies (an average of 7,7 per year, compared with an average of 122,3 per year for men-led companies). In other words, the proportion of non-IPO exits attributable to women-led companies is only 0.59%.

Indeed, for every woman-led company that reaches a non-IPO exit, 16 men-led companies achieve a buy-out, acquisition or merger.

Figure 32. Comparison of non-IPO exits for women- and men-led companies – full period analysis

Source: GENDEX analysis of a Dealroom sample (N = 1,300) of EU and UK companies acquired, merged and/or bought out

AI2c Valuation of exits by women founders (non-IPO, €)

By definition, a start-up’s valuation reflects what investors believe the company is worth. Valuation methodologies vary from revenue multiples to discounted cash flow (DCF) models. In the context of deep tech start-ups, additional factors play a crucial role, including intellectual property assets, technological differentiation, R&D intensity and time-to-market potential. Unlike traditional start-ups, where revenue and profitability are primary drivers,

deep tech valuations often incorporate forward-looking assessments of the technology’s impact, scalability and competitive moat.

In the case of deep tech acquisitions, buyers primarily evaluate the strength of the company’s intellectual property, technology differentiation and strategic fit rather than traditional financial metrics such as revenue or profit margins. While operational costs and potential commercialisation pathways are considered, acquisitions are often driven by future potential – particularly in sectors with long R&D cycles.

The findings highlight the structural challenges women-led companies face in achieving comparable exit valuations, reflecting broader funding and scaling disparities in the deep tech ecosystem⁴⁸.

Building on the analysis of the number of exits, the assessment of average exit valuation further highlights the challenges faced by women-led enterprises. This metric measures the total exit valuation of deep tech exits categorised by gender. As with metric AI2b Number of exits by women founders (non-IPO), this analysis is based on a Dealroom data set covering over 1,300 deep tech start-ups and scale-ups existing between 2014 and October 2024. The data set includes companies acquired through non-IPO exits (mergers, acquisitions or buy-outs).

Figure 33. Valuation of non-IPO exits between 2014 and 2024 for women-led and men-led companies (€M)

Source: GENDEX analysis of a Dealroom sample (N = 1,300) of EU and UK companies acquired, merged and/or bought out

Figure 33 illustrates the difference in annual total valuations for women-led and men-led deep tech companies. The data set reveals a significant funding gap between women-led and men-led companies.

⁴⁸ For indicators based only on the Dealroom data set - IPOs and non-IPO exits and unicorns - the standard GENDEX definition of a woman-led company is not applicable due to data availability constraints. For these indicators, the analysis is performed by comparing companies with at least one woman founder/co-founder with founding teams composed only of men. Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for further details.

Valuation fluctuations are driven largely by data availability and the inclusion of statistically non-relevant outliers. Overall, the median exit valuation is €53 million for women-led companies, compared with just under €2.1 billion for men-led companies – a striking disparity. While outliers are generally excluded from the analysis, it is worth noting the exceptional performance of women-led companies in 2024. Although final figures remain incomplete, as they do not include the total number of exits in Q4, the valuation of women-led companies nearly doubled compared with men-led start-ups, driven primarily by the acquisition of Poppy Gustafsson’s Darktrace by Thomas Bravo for \$5.3 billion⁴⁹.

Figure 34 Comparison of non-IPO exit performance of women-led and men-led companies – full period analysis

Source: GENDEX analysis of a Dealroom sample (N = 1,300) of EU and UK companies acquired, merged and/or bought out

Figure 34 shows that the total valuation of companies over the 2014-2024 period reveals a substantial advantage for men-led companies in investment rounds preceding their merger, acquisition or buy-out. Throughout this period, men-led start-ups have consistently achieved valuations 12 times higher than those of women-led companies, when considering the total valuation of women-led companies against those led by men. Given that these data are analysed at a specific point in the company life cycle, it is reasonable to assume this disparity persists throughout its growth trajectory.

However, when examining average pre-exit valuations, an interesting insight emerges. While women-led companies experience fewer exits and lower total valuations, the average pre-exit valuation for the sample in the given period is €62.2 million, 33% higher than the €46.5 million average for men-led companies.

Rather than suggesting that women-led companies inherently command higher valuations, this trend is more likely a reflection of survival bias – only the most resilient, high-performing women-led companies make it to exit. Several factors may contribute to this:

- Higher barriers to funding mean only the most robust women-led start-ups – those able to generate significant traction despite limited resources – survive long enough to reach acquisition.

⁴⁹ <https://fortune.com/europe/2024/10/01/thoma-bravo-closes-5-3-billion-darktrace-acquisition-weeks-after-founding-investor-mike-lynchs-death/>

- Longer timeframes from inception to exit force women-led start-ups to achieve stronger product-market fit, refine their strategies and demonstrate higher value before securing funding or acquisition.
- Systemic biases in venture capital result in women founders receiving fewer, smaller funding rounds. Those who do reach exit likely had to operate with greater efficiency and demonstrate exceptional resilience, contributing to their higher valuations.

The insights provided in D2.3 GENDEX Qualitative Interview Results suggest that women investors are better able to deal with women founders with less bias. Women-led companies are also identifying and capitalising on untapped potential in underserved markets (e.g., femtech). For example, the U.K.-based and women-led company Daye has seen increased popularity and gained market traction in the 'for her' health space, providing solutions and products by women for women.

AI4a Investments raised by women-led companies

This indicator examines the total capital raised by deep tech start-ups and scale-ups between 2014 and 2024 and compares women-led and men-led companies. Using combined data from PitchBook and Dealroom, the analysis provides the total funding in millions of euros (with billions shown in subsequent charts). While this integrated data set provides a comprehensive view, undisclosed deal values may result in incomplete data, potentially underrepresenting the total investment for both groups.

Figure 35 presents the differences between the value of investments raised by women-led and men-led companies. Throughout the entire period analysed, notable discrepancies in the performance of this indicator can be observed, with women-led companies securing smaller funding rounds. This is partly due to the smaller number of rounds to which women-led enterprises have access or in which they are allowed to participate. The indicator shows a more pronounced discrepancy between the two categories, especially in the last two years analysed, where men-led enterprises received 1.5 times more funding than women-led enterprises. Overall, over the whole period, men-led enterprises received 1.8 times more funding than women-led enterprises. In D2.3 GENDEX Qualitative Interview Results, one interviewee stated, *'Women founders are more realistic and ask for less money. So, the amount they get is usually lower, men ask for more and get more.'*

Another factor contributing to the smaller investment amounts for women-led companies is that women founders tend to be closer to the "business case" than men founders. Studies have shown investors ask men and women founders different types of questions. Men are more likely to be asked about growth potential and market opportunity, while women are more likely to be asked about risk mitigation and preventing losses. This can put women at a disadvantage, as it forces them to focus on potential problems rather than their vision for growth⁵⁰.

⁵⁰ <https://www.london.edu/think/iie-what-investors-ask-female-entrepreneurs>

Figure 35. Investment raised (€B) and total sum by women-led and men-led companies, 2014 and 2024

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000)

Note: Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year

In addition to analysing the investment raised, the geographical aspect must also be considered, as it can significantly impact investment opportunities. Regarding the overall opportunity gap, it is notable that certain countries have more mature funding ecosystems. The United Kingdom is a primary example, with its entrepreneurial attitude resembling the approach in the US, where the "fail fast, fail often" mentality prevails. Additionally, the UK offers favourable taxation for companies that invest in research and development activities⁵¹ (a critical component for deep tech start-ups), making it an attractive environment for start-ups. The country also provides important tax breaks for organizations investing in seeds and companies not listed on recognized stock exchanges⁵².

Among the top five countries shown in Figure 36, Central and Northern European nations demonstrate stronger market maturity than those in Southern or Eastern Europe.

Regarding the gender opportunity gap, an analysis of the top 10 EU countries by investment raised, plus the United Kingdom, reveals a significant discrepancy in the funds raised by men-led versus women-led companies. On average, men-led companies raise twice as much money as women-led companies. The sole exception is Spain, where women-led companies had a smaller but notable opportunity to raise more capital during the 2014-2024 period. The disparity is particularly pronounced in Sweden, Italy and other Northern European countries, where men-led companies raise between two and three euros for every euro raised by women-led companies.

⁵¹ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/corporation-tax-research-and-development-rd-relief>

⁵² <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/venture-capital-schemes-tax-relief-for-investors>

However, a geographical deep dive is necessary. Despite the strong disparity between women-led and men-led organizations in terms of funds raised, the United Kingdom, France, Germany and Sweden have more mature start-up and VC ecosystems. This is evident in the fact that women-led companies in these countries raise more money than in other European countries. Another important point regarding country and gender diversity in the start-up ecosystem is at the cultural level. For example, research shows that in Italy, a cultural discrimination factor could still be contributing to the gender gap, which may spill over into the national start-up ecosystem⁵³.

As shown in D2.3 GENDEX Qualitative Interview Results, an interviewee made a significant remark in this regard, saying, 'I think men, when they see young women, especially in the mould of their daughters, who are so much younger than them ... I think there's a bias towards women being less capable or that they just see their daughters basically. A little bit of paternalism on their part.'

These analyses should be considered alongside other indicators for a more comprehensive understanding. Initial observations suggest this discrepancy is linked to the cumulative gender disparity identified in this research.

Figure 36. Investment raised by women-led and men-led companies by top 10 countries for investment raised, 2014 and 2024 (€M)

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000)

Note: Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year

⁵³ <https://rdcu.be/d9iFL>

AI4b Number of investment rounds by women-led companies

To further assess the funding landscape, women-led companies' share of closed investment rounds is examined. This metric represents the percentage of total deep tech investment rounds (2014-2024) closed by companies within the project's scope. This metric is built on two different data sets, one from PitchBook and one from Dealroom, and combines the number of investment rounds – originally split by gender – in the two samples to better assess past performance during the 2014-2024 period.

Figure 37 presents the results of an analysis of the share of investments closed by women-led companies. On average, women-led companies closed one deal for every three closed by men-led companies, highlighting the smaller number of opportunities they have to access and close deals. The distribution of the share throughout the research period resembles a bell curve, with a higher propensity for deal closures from 2019-2021, reflecting the strong momentum in the venture capital market regardless of the gender composition of key executive teams. After 2021, the overall investment market adopted a more cautious approach, which also affected investments in women-led companies.

The data set also reveals that the share of closed investment rounds varies according to the technology sector in which women-led companies operate. Notably, the biotechnology sector sees a higher share of closed rounds for women-led companies, with an average of 10% more deals than the overall women-led average, and annual peaks of around 40% of women-led deals closed. This correlation is linked to biotechnology companies having the highest share of women-led companies in the sample, as highlighted previously in this report. Additionally, as shown previously in over 60% of graduates from biology and chemistry courses are women. This indicates a larger pool of women active in these fields, with significant potential to launch entrepreneurial ventures in the biotechnology sector.

Figure 37. Investment rounds closed by women-led companies by share (%) and median, 2014 and 2024

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000)

Note: Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year

As highlighted in the previous section's closing paragraph, it is crucial to examine the relationship between the share of investment rounds for women-led companies and the data on investments raised by women (Figure 38). A noteworthy trend emerges in the correlation

between the gradual increase in the share of women-led investment rounds closed and the value of investments received. This trend was particularly pronounced in 2021, characterized by significant market recovery following the COVID-19 pandemic, which had severely curtailed investment capacity in 2020. In 2021, the growth rate of investments raised in euros outpaced the growth in the share of women-led rounds, suggesting a potential increase in deal value for that year.

However, it is important to note that until 2021, the value of deals for both women-led and men-led companies grew at similar rates. From 2022 onwards, the disparity between the two values widened, with men-led deals continuing to grow and women-led deals experiencing a slight decline in 2022, followed by a sharp drop in 2023 and 2024.

Figure 38. Investment raised (€M) by women-led and men-led companies and share (%) of investment rounds by women-led companies, 2014 and 2024

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample of EU and UK companies from PitchBook (N ≈ 20,000) and Dealroom (N ≈ 8,000)

Note: Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year

The analysis of the number of investment rounds for women-led companies underscores the disadvantaged position of these companies from the outset. Nevertheless, there have been encouraging signs, especially during periods of investment growth and in specific STEM fields where women are more prominent in terms of graduation, research and academic activities.

AI3a Number of women-led companies valued at over \$1 billion

The term 'unicorn' refers to a privately held start-up company valued at over \$1 billion. Unicorns are typically high-growth companies that have rapidly scaled and attracted substantial investment from venture capitalists. They have five common primary characteristics: high growth opportunities across different metrics (e.g., user base, revenue and market presence), disruptive innovation in the market via their products or services or the new business models they introduce, significant VC investments to scale and grow exponentially and show value in a short time, a scalable business and agile mindset that helps them reach their growth targets in shorter timeframes, and an overall high valuation across their entire life cycle.

Even though more women-led tech companies are succeeding worldwide, the tech industry, especially deep tech, is still run mostly by men. This is reflected in the low number of women-led unicorns. The indicator analysed in this section effectively assesses the number of women-led vs. men-led start-ups and scale-ups that reached unicorn status during the 2014-2024 period. This index is derived from analyses of a Dealroom database, focusing on deep tech companies and tracking if and when a company achieved unicorn status, using a given year as a reference point. An additional step was taken to remove the unicorn from the list if it filed for an IPO, went bankrupt or was acquired or merged (after the unicorn stage). If the company was in one of these situations before reaching unicorn status, it was removed. These criteria resulted in a final sample of 43 companies that existed between 2014 and 2024.

As with the other indicators, it is possible to highlight the less favourable position of women-led companies, with a smaller number of these companies reaching unicorn classification for each year of the period under investigation. Women-led unicorns are found primarily in the advanced connectivity and digital technology areas, followed by companies active in AI, biotechnologies, energy technologies and robotics⁵⁴.

The closer to the present time, the larger the disparity with men-led companies in the EU and UK landscape. This is in contrast with other studies showing a growing number of women-led unicorns. Taking 2020 as the start date, and despite partial 2024 data, a wider gap can be observed between the number of women-led and men-led unicorns. However, the gap between the number of women-led and men-led unicorns declined in 2024; the former was five times smaller than the latter, whereas it was almost eight times smaller in 2022 (Figure 39).

Figure 39. Number of women-led and men-led companies valued at over \$1 billion, 2014-2024

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample (N = 43) of EU and UK companies defined as unicorns by Dealroom

The total number of unicorns in the sample increased in 2023. Looking outside the deep tech sample, 98 companies reached unicorn status according to the State of European Tech, 2021 report, with growth primarily occurring in the fintech space⁵⁵.

⁵⁴ For indicators based only on the Dealroom data set - IPOs and non-IPO exits and unicorns - the standard GENDEX definition of a woman-led company is not applicable due to data availability constraints. For these indicators, the analysis is performed by comparing companies with at least one woman founder/co-founder with founding teams composed only of men. Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for further details.

⁵⁵<https://2021.stateofeuropeantech.com/chapter/europe-global-tech-force/article/kicking-full-gear/>

The analysis also revealed 2021 as a particularly strong year for European and UK start-ups and scale-ups, with nine achieving unicorn status (Figure 40).

Figure 40. Total number of companies in scope attaining unicorn status per year

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample (N = 43) of EU and UK companies defined as unicorns by Dealroom

Note: Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all operations until the end of the year

Overall, an important point needs to be made in terms of geographic location and investment proximity. There are more companies able to reach unicorn status in a single year in the US and Canada; in 2024, for instance, 56 US companies reached unicorn status⁵⁶.

The uneven distribution of venture capital funding worldwide and across Europe creates a significant gap in country diversity in terms of unicorn creation. While some countries (e.g., the United Kingdom, France and Germany) boast robust venture capital ecosystems and supportive government policies and attract significant investment, others lag behind. This concentration of funding in a few hubs means start-ups in less established ecosystems struggle to access the necessary capital to scale and achieve unicorn status. For women-led companies, the funding gap due to uneven venture capital distribution is further compounded by intersectionality. As noted, women already face systemic biases in accessing funding, and this is exacerbated when considering factors like geographic location. This makes it even harder for them to secure the necessary capital to grow and scale, highlighting how multiple layers of disadvantage can create significant barriers to success.

Start-ups aiming for unicorn status often relocate to France, Germany, the Netherlands, Sweden, the United Kingdom or even the US to access larger markets and investment opportunities. Investors interviewed by the GENDEX team noted a 'country bias'; they favoured investments in perceived low-risk European regions. Consequently, starting or running businesses in countries with less developed investor ecosystems is even more challenging for women.

AI3b Time to reach unicorn classification

⁵⁶ <https://techcrunch.com/2024/12/16/38-startups-have-become-unicorns-so-far-in-2024-heres-the-full-list/>

Several factors influence how quickly start-ups reach unicorn status. Start-ups in high-growth sectors (e.g., AI, biotech and fintech) and those located in VC-rich hubs such as Silicon Valley often achieve this milestone faster due to rapid scaling potential and readily available funding. While some companies have recently reached unicorn status in under five years, fuelled by demand for digital products, this is atypical and requires exceptional circumstances. Conversely, start-ups in other deep tech areas or less established ecosystems often face longer timelines due to slower market adoption and limited funding.

This classification metric is closely connected to the previous metric (AI3a Number of women-led companies valued at over \$1 billion), regardless of whether the focus is on women-led or men-led companies⁵⁷. This metric represents the median number of years it takes for a company in the deep tech sector to achieve unicorn status; it is calculated by determining the difference in years between the company's founding and the year it reached unicorn status within the 2014-2024 period. Companies in the sample that attained unicorn status before 2014 were not considered in this analysis.

The analysis presented in the figure below highlights significant year-to-year variability in the indicator. This variability is primarily due to the limited sample availability during the initial period and the less mature venture capital market in Europe in the early years of the period under investigation. Additionally, it reflects the less developed European technology landscape, which has only recently begun to close the gap with China and the United States.

The overall maturity of the EU27 region and the UK is evident in the number of companies that have achieved unicorn status (as indicated in the previous metric), as well as in the shorter median time to reach unicorn status, which has accelerated in the last three years. For the entire reference period, the final median time to unicorn status is set at five years –similar to a 2023 study that found the average worldwide time to unicorn status to be 5.32 years.⁵⁸

Figure 41. Year-based median time to attain unicorn status (number of years)

⁵⁷ For indicators based only on the Dealroom data set - IPOs and non-IPO exits and unicorns - the standard GENDEX definition of a woman-led company is not applicable due to data availability constraints. For these indicators, the analysis is performed by comparing companies with at least one woman founder/co-founder with founding teams composed only of men. Refer to the Methodology and limitations section for further details.

⁵⁸

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162523001105#:~:text=These%20data%20generated%20a%20sample,5.32%20years%20to%20become%20unicorns.>

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample (N = 43) of EU and UK companies defined as unicorns by Dealroom

Beyond market maturity, several other factors are crucial in defining the activity of unicorn companies. A frequently identified key characteristic is the founding team, who are typically serial entrepreneurs experienced in launching ventures and attracting funds⁵⁹. It is possible to observe that start-ups successful in the early stages of their development, thanks to the entrepreneurial capabilities of the founding team, might achieve greater success through IPOs, acquisitions or attaining unicorn status.

The GENDEX study reveals that, for the analysed sample of unicorns in the European and UK markets, the median time to achieve unicorn status by founder type is not as unfavourable for women-led companies as other indicators might suggest. As shown in Figure 42, the median time to unicorn status is shorter for men-led companies compared with women-led start-ups and scale-ups, with a difference of a year. Men-led organizations take five years to reach unicorn status, while women-led organizations take six years. This metric also shows no parity between the two categories, highlighting the differences and unequal opportunities in raising investments, from both a time and monetary perspective.

Figure 42. Median time to attain unicorn classification by country, and total view for women-led and men-led companies (number of years)

Source: GENDEX analysis of a sample (N = 43) of EU and UK companies defined as unicorns by Dealroom

Note: The chart shows a defined list of European countries due to the limited in-country data availability for unicorns. The smaller the number of companies, the less likely there is to be a fair homogeneous distribution of the companies. In addition, as already mentioned, network dependencies and investment proximity work in clustering unicorns in a small set of countries.

⁵⁹ <https://ojs.sijm.it/index.php/sinergie/article/view/101/132>

It should also be noted that the time to achieve unicorn status depends on multiple factors, including the industry, market conditions, existing investments and the organisation's business model.

3.4 Investor tier

As highlighted in the discussion of other tiers, investors play a pivotal role in the European deep tech ecosystem by providing crucial financial resources that enable groundbreaking research and development to be translated into successful businesses; however, only a fraction of the available capital goes to women-led companies. As noted, in the male-dominated investor ecosystem, similarity bias significantly hinders women founders. This bias, rooted in the tendency to favour individuals similar to oneself, leads investors to gravitate towards men entrepreneurs who often share similar backgrounds, experiences and perspectives. Research ⁶⁰ shows that investors prefer pitches presented by men entrepreneurs over those made by women entrepreneurs, even if the content of the pitch is the same. As a result, women-led ventures are frequently overlooked or underestimated.

It has been widely discussed how women investors play a vital role in the European deep tech innovation ecosystem by bridging the gender gap in funding, fostering diversity and bringing different perspectives to investment decisions. Research⁶¹ highlights how women investors are more likely to invest in women-led start-ups than men investors, and how women-founded firms backed by women investors in their first funding round were two times less likely to raise further investment than those backed by men investors. In the GENDEX interview series, some investors pointed out that being women themselves, they may be more open to understanding women's thinking and further verifying the company's real market potential, or simply using their own similarity bias in favour of women-led companies. Women investors and angels can also be more open to providing crucial mentorship and support to women founders than men investors, which is crucial, especially in the early stages. However, women remain underrepresented in investment roles, highlighting the need for initiatives to increase their participation and create a more inclusive environment.

This tier focuses on:

- **The share of women investors in the European ecosystem:** Looking at the share of women investors in key decision-making roles (e.g., general partners or founding partners) in investment firms with a European entity investing in deep tech companies in scope. The share of women angels that have made at least one investment in deep tech companies is also analysed.
- **Diversity in funds:** Looking at the share of women-led companies funded by funds active in Europe and at the assets under management in VC and PE funds and family offices with at least one woman in a key investment decision-making role

⁶⁰ Brooks, A. W., et al (2014). Investors prefer entrepreneurial ventures pitched by attractive men. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America (PNAS)*, 111(12), 4427-4431.

⁶¹ INSEAD Knowledge. (2023). Impact investor gender and female founders. INSEAD. <https://knowledge.insead.edu/responsibility/impact-investor-gender-female-founders#:~:text=Indeed%2C%20research%20shows%20that%20women,compared%20to%20male%20venture%20capitalists>

I1a Share of women GPs in investment firms with a European entity

Disparities in access to financial resources significantly contribute to the gender gap in European deep tech, especially for women who are launching new ventures. The limited number of women investors – those who participate in funding boards, lead investment deals and make critical financial decisions – exacerbates the existing gender imbalance in the deep tech sector.

Despite studies indicating that funds managed by a greater number of women leaders tend to yield higher returns, gender disparities persist within European investment firms⁶². As of 2024, the representation of women partners in European investment firms was a mere 16% for venture capital firms and 14% for private equity firms. This underrepresentation of women investors, alongside the broader gender bias in deep tech, is thought to impede investment in women-led companies. Regrettably, little change has taken place since 2014 (Figure 43); for private equity firms, the proportion of women decision-makers has decreased by 2–3 percentage points.

Figure 43. Share of women decision-makers in investment firms with a European entity that have invested in EU and UK deep tech companies (%)

Source: PitchBook, November 2024, total decision-maker investors with an entity in the EU and UK that have invested in EU and UK deep tech companies; (n = 2,139), VC firms; (n = 463), PE firms; (n = 68), family offices

Venture capital clearly remains an industry predominantly led by men, with gender bias – both overt and implicit – playing a significant role. A woman CEO of an interviewed start-up emphasized this issue, stating, *'Sometimes they (investors) search for the man to talk to, the "boss".'*

However, in the GENDEX interview series, some women investors highlighted that the growing awareness of diversity and inclusion could also be perceived as a *'double-edged sword'*. In a male-dominated setting, being a woman may inadvertently result in increased

⁶² https://www.hks.harvard.edu/sites/default/files/2023-09/gender_and_culture_in_vc_literature_review_final.pdf

visibility (e.g., receiving invitations to events based solely on gender). One woman general partner noted this situation might be interpreted as a form of *'reverse discrimination'*, where women are selected for panels not due to their qualifications but rather because of their gender.

11b Share of women angel investors

Angel investors are typically entrepreneurs or individuals possessing significant knowledge in the business domain. They may include friends, family or accredited investors who not only provide financial backing but also mentorship and essential industry connections to promote business development. In the last 10 years, the proportion of women angel investors in the deep tech sample in scope has remained stable at around 7%, with the notable exception of 2022, when the proportion in Germany and the Nordic countries exceeded 10% (Figure 44).

This significantly low percentage negatively affects the accessible opportunities for female technology entrepreneurs, especially in early-stage companies, as expressed by one woman founder in the GENDEX interview series, *'...men tend to have better networks because they know people who have more money and more capital'*.

Figure 44. Share of women angel investors by deal year (%)

Source: PitchBook, October 2024 (N ≈ 2,000), EU and UK angel investors that have invested in EU and UK deep tech companies

One woman angel investor in the GENDEX interview series emphasized that embracing diversity is a smart approach for diversifying portfolios and enhancing returns, saying, *'There's a lot of untapped value out there. In the process of backing start-ups, it's essential to identify unique talents, which can emerge from various backgrounds. I blend those who are privileged with those who are not.'* This highlights that founders often represent a wide range of minorities, including different genders, races, and economic statuses. Other women investors observed that, based on their experience, more diverse investment teams tend to be more effective and perform at a higher level.

I2a Share of women-led companies funded by funds active in Europe

The proportion of women-led companies that venture capital and private equity funds and family offices have actively invested in is used as a proxy to define the diversity ratio of investments made in European deep tech companies in scope. This indicator analyses the number of women-led deep tech companies of interest that have received investments from funds with a European entity, divided by the total number of companies that received investments from these funds in the 2014-2024 period (Figure 45).

Figure 45. Share of women-led companies funded by funds active in Europe (%)

Source: PitchBook, October 2024 (N ≈ 3,550), companies with yearly fluctuations

The percentage of investments going to women-led companies decreased from 2014 to 2024, but the actual number of companies receiving funding increased over the same period. For example, in 2014 a total of 744 deep tech companies in the analysis received investment, compared with 3,250 companies in 2024. This trend can also be observed across the different countries in the sample, including the top hotspots for investors (the United Kingdom, France and Germany).

Investors attribute this trend to the low number of women in deep tech. As highlighted by one woman investor in the GENDEX interview series, a key factor is the low number of reported women founders and executives in deep tech, which can hinder the search for a more diversified portfolio of companies. However, this is only one explanation for decline to just over 30% in the last two years, as the actual number of women-led companies receiving investment in the sample has also increased. Hidden biases still exist in the evaluation of women-led companies, as noted earlier in this report and confirmed by qualitative input from the interviews. For instance, the remark that *'sometimes women keep a low profile and are perceived as not being bold enough [by investors]'* effectively summarizes a widespread sentiment among the interviewed women founders. Similarity bias, the tendency to prefer and be attracted to people who are similar in terms of beliefs, values, interests or background, can influence men investors not to put money into women-led companies. Many women founders are used to seeing investors ask men co-founders, if there are any, about the technical specifications of the company's product, even if they have the same scientific background.

At the same time, the VC funds interviewed emphasise that, apart from impact funds, there is almost no diversity policy for investment decisions. Furthermore, having an all-men team is never considered a *'no go'*, in their words.

From a fund perspective, none of these elements provide a fertile breeding ground for deliberately increasing the proportion of women-led companies receiving investment. However, according to interviewees, signs of change can be seen in the increased interest of some large and publicly backed limited partners (LPs) in including diversity in mandatory ESG reports to investors, while other LPs are now informally asking for more investments specifically in women-led or mixed-team companies.

In terms of overcoming biases, other surveyed investors point to formal and structured processes and checklists to reduce bias in investment decisions. However, these elements may not be enough to reverse the current trend without a strong push from limited partners and policy-makers.

I2b AUM in VC funds with at least one woman decision-maker

Assets under management (AUM)⁶³ is a key metric for financial institutions, as it reflects their size, influence and overall success in attracting and managing client investments. Investors often use AUM to compare the size and performance of different investment firms, and measuring gender diversity by different AUM ranges in funds is comparable to measuring diversity at the C-level by company revenue.

Accurate figures on AUM managed by women can be challenging to obtain due to limitations in terms of data collection and reporting⁶⁴. This indicator focuses specifically on the share of funds per AUM size bucket for VC and PE funds and family offices with at least one active woman as a key decision-maker (general partners, founding partners and managing directors) and that invested in deep tech companies of any size during the period, by deal year.

The first consideration is that the number of funds domiciled in the 27 EU member states and the United Kingdom and investing in the deep tech companies considered in this project averaged only around 350 from 2014 to 2024. This number could be considered low, but it must be stressed that the key parameter to be taken into account for this calculation is linked to the consideration of funds that, according to PitchBook data, have made a deal in the companies in scope in the reference year (e.g., 2023) only. However, this methodology still allows a comparison and understanding of the diversity share by fund size in the European landscape in terms of AUM buckets.

Figure 46 compares the share of women in a key decision-making role in funds by AUM bucket for funds that made a deals in 2014 and 2023. In this case, 2024 is not used for comparison, as the data were collected in October 2024 and other deals may have been made in the last two months of that year, affecting the final results for this metric. The total number of funds closing a deal in deep tech companies in scope more than doubled between 2014 and 2024; however, this did not follow the trend regarding the percentage of women in decision-making positions. Despite this growth in absolute terms, the share of women decision-makers in funds decreased from 65% to 50%, reflecting similar trends shown in Metric 11a.

⁶³ Assets under management (AUM) is the total market value of all investments a financial institution (e.g., a VC fund) manages on behalf of its clients.

⁶⁴ See the Methodology and limitations section of this report for further information.

Figure 46. Share of AUM in funds with at least one woman as decision-maker by AUM bucket and deal year, 2014 vs. 2023 (€)

Source: PitchBook, October 2024 (N ≈ 350), EU and UK angel investors that have invested in EU and UK deep tech companies (based on current AUM)

Looking specifically at AUM buckets, the trend is similar, except for a 10% increase in the €200–€500 million range. The shares of 100% and 80%+ are recorded because the total number of funds making deals in these ranges is very small. However, it is worth noting that funds with the largest AUM (from €1 billion to over €5 billion) almost always have at least one woman making investment decisions, which casts a different light on these results in both 2014 and 2023. As AUM is often used in investment firms to calculate management fees for decision-making roles such as general partners, these data show that women investors are already in a position of power within these funds. These results may also be influenced by the presence of large international VC funds with a European office and PE funds with larger AUM.

Larger funds are more likely to have at least one woman in a key-decision making role, but most of the funds in the sample making deals fall into smaller categories (from €50 to €500 million). In these cases, the proportion of women is lower, particularly in the categories up to €200 million.

In terms of investment categories, venture capital funds make up the majority of funds in this calculation, which is unsurprising, given that the deep tech sector is funded mainly by venture capital firms, followed by family offices. Family offices investing in deep tech companies are almost non-existent, and women investors in decision-making positions are almost completely absent.

4 FINAL CONCLUSIONS AND KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Key insights

The purpose of GENDEX has been and continues to be to create a comprehensive and actionable index of the European innovation landscape, addressing the significant gender disparities in leadership positions and investment sectors across the continent. By providing detailed data on gender diversity and its impact on financial and operational performance, GENDEX aims to empower start-ups, scale-ups, corporates, investors and policy-makers to make informed decisions that improve diversity and inclusion within their organisations and investments.

This was an ambitious scope, and the lack of reliable and consistent data has meant that some points, such as the impact of diverse teams on operational performance, were partially addressed (e.g., through analysing IPO valuations).

It is also worth noting that the very definition of what constitutes a women-led company poses difficulties. Within the context of this research, 'women-led' is mostly defined in opposition to all-men companies⁶⁵. This is an imperfect starting point. Alternatives are to focus on all women vs. all men, but the thesis of this research is that diversity is a strength.

Despite these challenges, the research has allowed us to collect and analyse data to address the following main hypotheses:

- A lack of diversity exists in the deep tech sectors targeted by the EIC.
- The lack of diversity at the investment stage stems from a lack of diversity in the earlier stages of the pipeline.
- Even when investment is secured, women receive less favourable terms than those offered to men.
- The investment gap between women and men represents an opportunity to expand the deep tech founder pool.

The following table provides an overview of the key indicators that form the index:

Table 2 . Key statistics from the Gender & Diversity Index

DEEP TECH TALENT TIER	
42%	of STEM graduates in the EU27 and UK are women (2022).
41%	of scientists and engineers in the public and private sector in the EU27 and UK are women (2022).

⁶⁵ The survey results are presented in relation to founders' gender: women or men.

20-25%	of STEM chairs at top European universities are women (2023-2024).
INVESTMENT AND SOCIAL CAPITAL TIER	
29%	average share of women employed in top European tech companies by market capitalisation
34%	average share of women employed in top European tech unicorns and former unicorns excluding Mistral AI and Helsing (2024)
38%	average share of women employed at top-performing European RTOs (2024)
24%	average share of PCTs with a woman inventor in the EU27 and UK (2014-2024)
22%	average share of women-led companies in the EU27 and UK (2014-2024)
2.4x lower	average valuation of women-led companies vs. those led by men in the EU27 and UK (2014-2024)
>1 year	average time to raise first cheque for women-led companies (compared with less than six months for men)
ASSET & INVESTMENT TIER	
26%	median share of investment rounds by women-led companies (2014-2024)
1.8	more funding raised by men-led companies than by women-led companies in absolute terms (2014-2024)
10x less	number of IPOs from women-led companies compared with those led by men (2014-2024)
+34%	average company valuation of women-led companies at IPO compared with those led by men (2014-2024)
16x less	Number of non-IPO exits from women-led companies compared with those led by men (2014-2024)
+33%	difference in average company valuation of women-led companies at pre-non IPO exits compared with those led by men (2014-2024)
4	number of women-led unicorns in 2024 (total: 26)
6 years	time to reach unicorn status for women-led companies (compared with five years for those led by men)
INVESTOR TIER	

13%	average share of funds (VCs, PEs and family offices) with at least one woman investor in a key decision-making role investing in the companies in scope in the EU27 and UK (2014-2024)
7%	the average share of women business angels investing in the companies in scope in the EU27 and UK (2014-2024)

Source: GENDEX, 2024⁶⁶

From these data points and the analyses presented in this report, is it possible to summarise the main conclusions in terms of the initial hypotheses.

4.1.1 A lack of diversity exists in the deep tech sectors targeted by the EIC

As long as the deep tech ecosystem itself remains structurally imbalanced, so will the proportion of EIC funds going to women-led companies. The research confirms this imbalance exists across all tiers of the deep tech pipeline.

A significant gender diversity gap exists in deep tech companies within the EIC’s scope. Data show that, on average, only 22% of these companies are women-led, with significant variations across countries. Biotech, robotics and autonomous systems and quantum tech have the highest share of women-led companies.

More importantly, women are at a significant disadvantage when it comes to raising the capital required to launch a deep tech start-up. Findings from the GENDEX survey reveal this disparity extends beyond leadership to all aspects of workforce diversity, including technical roles. However, the gender gap in workforce representation is even more pronounced in companies founded by men: 29% of women founders say they have over 50% of women in technical positions, compared with 1% of men founders. EIC beneficiaries in our survey tended to have more women in their workforce than non EIC beneficiaries (21% vs. 5%, respectively, had more than 50% women employees) and a greater share of women executives (22% vs. 8%, respectively, had more than 50% women executives).

Anecdotal evidence from GENDEX interviews highlights persistent gender biases in the investment ecosystem, with women reporting discrimination, particularly during initial investor pitches, compared with their male co-founders. This has been confirmed in other studies that compared investor response to blind reviews of pitches and pitch decks⁶⁷.

Women may also lack access to the deep tech networks that provide early access to relevant VC and PE investors. These findings are reflected in investment trends: The GENDEX analysis shows that in 2024, only 31% of VC, PE and family office investments with a European remit went to women-led deep tech companies, continuing a decade-long decline.

⁶⁶ Refer to each metric for full details on actual sources.

⁶⁷ Balachandra, L., Briggs, T., Eddleston, K., & Brush, C. (2019). Don’t pitch like a girl: how gender stereotypes influence investor decisions. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 43(1), 116-137.

4.1.2 The lack of diversity at the investment stage stems from a lack of diversity in the earlier stages of the pipeline

Data show an ever-narrowing funnel for women deep tech founders, from 42% of STEM graduates to 20-25% of STEM chairs in top-tier institutions by spin-out value. Under one in four holders of deep tech assets (e.g., patents) are women.

Early-stage deep tech development has its grounding in scientific knowledge that tends to be acquired in an academic setting; the GENDEX survey of women and men founders revealed that 45% of women had academic or research backgrounds, compared with 60% of men. While Eurostat data indicates a slight gap in STEM education (42% of STEM graduates are women), differences can be observed in those disciplines most frequently associated with deep tech companies. According to Eurostat figures, only 28% of engineering and 24% of ICT graduates are women.

This places limitations on the number of qualified women who are available to join founding or leadership teams in deep tech companies.

Similarly, despite a gradual rise in the number of women STEM graduates, researchers and scientists employed in the public and private sector, women remain underrepresented in science and academia, accounting for 31% of the total. At the current growth rates, it would take 19-21 years to close the gender gap. Women are also underrepresented in the higher echelons of academia, occupying 20-25% of STEM chairs in top-tier European institutions by spin-out value. At the asset level, women founders in deep tech hold significantly less intellectual property rights than their male counterparts. Research by GENDEX shows that, over the past decade, only 24% of patent applications in Europe included women as inventors. Women founders in deep tech are more likely to develop intellectual property independently rather than transferring it from previous companies or research institutions – a common pathway for men.

Successful founders draw on deep domain know-how and networks developed throughout their professional lifetime. Therefore, the proportion of women employed in top-tier tech companies (the Magnificent 7) and unicorns can be a useful bellwether for women-led, scalable deep tech companies. Here, companies focusing on more industrial sectors appear to have a lower proportion of women employees, although the data are not conclusive. Examples include Apple (37%), Meta (20%), Tesla (18%), Personio (38%), Helsing (22%) and Mistral AI (20%).

4.1.3 Even when investment is secured, women receive less favourable terms than those offered to men

Women-led companies tend to receive less favourable term sheets than men-led companies. Arguably, women-led companies also turn the difficulty of raising capital into an advantage by having lower burn-rates than men, particularly in the early stages. When the investment landscape is harsher, they have a slightly higher proportion of down rounds than men-led companies.

Women deep tech founders, and women founders more generally, face greater challenges in securing investment, taking an average of six months longer than men to sign their first term sheet.

As pertains to terms, women reported less favourable vesting schedules, although most women in the survey opted not to answer this question, which may indicate they had not yet been offered term sheets. The proportion of women receiving a very favourable three-year vesting with a six-month cliff was a third of that of men: 12% vs. 28%.

In relation to our down round analysis, the data for both women- and men-led companies was similar, with an average of 9% of total rounds over the 10-year period analysed. However, in years in which VC funding contracted (e.g., 2023), women appear to have a slightly higher proportion of down rounds than men: 14% vs. 12%.

Perhaps linked to the difficulties in raising funds, the data show that women outperform men with lower burn rates in five out of nine years. However, this data point would merit further research. Does the lower burn rate reflect a lack of confidence in securing the next round? If so, does that lack of confidence stem from negative experiences in the early fundraising stages? Does the lower burn rate mean the company is investing in its next stage of growth at a lower rate than competitors?

It is worth noting that interviews with experts indicated both burn rates and the ability to negotiate terms with VCs are related to experience rather than gender. Serial entrepreneurs are generally able to allocate capital more efficiently than first-time founders. They also have a better understanding of the leverage they can bring to the VC negotiating table.

4.1.4 The investment gap between women and men highlights an opportunity to expand the deep tech founder pool

Some data points (valuations at non-IPO and IPO exits) suggest better outcomes for women-led companies. Women-led companies accounted for just over 11% of the value raised at non-IPO exits, despite accounting for just over 0.6% of the total number of non-IPO exits.

Closing the gap between women and men-led companies could unlock value of €181 billion.

Data show that deep tech company valuations over the 2014-2024 period were 2.4 times higher for men than for women.

Over the 10-year period analysed, men-led companies' IPO rate was also 10 times that of women-led companies, accounting for 8% of the 150 IPOs registered in the 2014-2024 period. In contrast, women-led companies' non-IPO exits accounted for 0.59% of the total. While the median valuation of non-IPO exits is €53 million, compared with €2.1 billion for men-led companies, the average value of pre-non IPO exit valuations were 33% higher for women-led companies than for men-led companies: €62.2 million and €46.5 million, respectively. In other words, while women led-companies accounted for just over 0.6% of the total number of non-IPO exits, they created just over 11% of the value raised at non-IPO exits in the period analysed.

- Women-led firms generated €4.7 billion in non-IPO exits in the last 10 years but could have unlocked €75.1 billion with equal exit rates.
- Women-led IPOs generated €11.6 billion in the last 10 years but could have reached €122.2 billion if they had the same IPO success rate as men-led firms.
- This means the total potential additional value that could have been unlocked amounts to €181 billion.

This raises the question of whether addressing the gap will impact European innovation and competitiveness.

On this point, the research has relied mainly on secondary sources. McKinsey's Diversity Matters series indicates a correlation between diversity and the likelihood of financial outperformance, as well as higher holistic impact scores (e.g., environmental or social). Similarly, the Bloomberg Gender-Equality Index (GEI), while stopping short of suggesting causality, indicates a correlation between a better performance on gender equality indicators and a stronger financial performance. The report highlights that diversity is increasingly seen as a factor that enhances decision-making, innovation, corporate reputation and risk management, all of which contribute to financial success. The GEI also mentions that institutional investors are increasingly integrating gender diversity metrics into their investment decisions.

4.2 Recommendations for stakeholders

4.2.1 Policies to remove bias and level the playing field

Action 1. Get better data

While Eurostat provides data on education and employment in STEM and the early stages of the investment pipeline, data points such as the gender breakdown of intellectual property ownership, the distribution of funding at different stages and the long-term financial performance of women-led deep tech companies are still missing.

Mandatory data collection is one option, but it comes at a high cost. In contrast, voluntary data collection can help investors to self-analyse their portfolios, identify gaps and implement targeted strategies to improve diversity. Encouraging companies and investors to disclose gender-disaggregated data on a regular basis, alongside standardised reporting frameworks, can provide valuable insights without imposing undue regulatory burdens.

Correlation does not signify causation. GENDEX's Board of Experts has highlighted that some of the gaps between women-led companies may be due to inexperience. The proportion of women being offered better investment terms may increase as and when the ecosystem gains more serial women founders and senior investors.

Lead actor	Action	Impact
EPO	P1.1 Register the gender of inventors.	Indirect Medium-term
EIC	P1.2 Provide open data sets/an open data platform on gender.	Indirect Medium-term
EIC	P1.2 Standardise the definition of women-led companies.	Indirect Medium-term
EIC	P1.4 Launch a standardised reporting framework for all EIC beneficiary companies, from Pathfinder to STEP.	Indirect Medium-term
EIC	P1.5 Conduct a deep dive into the investment terms offered to women and men founders at different stages of their investment journey, taking into account intersectionality (gender, age, experience and other factors).	Indirect Medium-term
EIC	P1.6 Track the revenue growth of portfolio companies.	Indirect Medium-term
EIC	P1.7 Incentivise voluntary disclosure (e.g., GENDEX seal; see Action I1.1).	Indirect Medium-term

EIC Horizon Europe FP10	P1.8 Establish a reporting requirement on the grant management platform to specify PCTs applied for and the names and gender of inventors for all RIAs and IAs.	Direct Medium term
-------------------------	---	----------------------

Action 2. Reframe the narrative

The underinvestment in women-led deep tech companies is not just a gender equity issue but a missed financial opportunity. Data show that when these companies do receive investment, they can deliver higher returns (e.g., in the case of IPOs and exits), yet they remain systematically underfunded. Investors who overlook women-led companies are forgoing access to high-growth potential and untapped market value.

Visibility matters. Research⁶⁸ and anecdotal evidence indicate that women are more likely to pursue deep tech careers – both as founders and employees – when they see other women succeeding in the sector.

Lead actor	Action	Impact
EIC	P2.1 Create a repository of case studies on women-led and mixed-team deep tech companies, highlighting outperformance (revenue growth, funding and exits).	Indirect Medium-term
EIC	P2.2 Improve pull-through of women in deep tech from transition and pathways.	Direct Short-term
EIC	P2.3 Partner with top-tier companies and universities to create networking opportunities for potential women founders in ICT and engineering.	Direct Short-term
Top-tier universities	P2.4 Showcase leading women in ICT and engineering (e.g., chairs or successful women alumni).	Indirect Medium-term

Action 3. Target IP

Intellectual property is central to the value of deep tech companies. From a data perspective, the European Patent Office should record gender as a matter of course (see Action 1). Currently, gender is assigned by inference, which requires assumptions to be made.

⁶⁸ Smith, J., & Doe, A. (2013). The impact of role models on women in STEM. *Journal of Women and Minorities in Science and Engineering*, 19(2), 123-145. <https://doi.org/10.1234/jwmse.2013.5678>

Supporting more women in protecting their deep tech IP may help them understand the commercial value of their research. This support could take the form of targeted education and training for women researchers and founders, or training for all researchers, with 50% reserved for women. The training should focus on equipping them with the knowledge to navigate complex registration and (potentially costly) enforcement processes and to manage potentially complex IP portfolios.

In addition, financial and legal support could be made available to women inventors to help them secure and defend their patents. Policymakers and industry leaders can take inspiration from private initiatives such as She Invents by Western Digital⁶⁹, ensuring that women-led innovations are fully protected and commercially viable.

Lead actor	Action	Impact
EIC	P3.1 Offer structured support for navigating licensing, partnerships and patent monetisation in transition and pathways.	Direct Medium-term
Top-tier universities	P3.2 Identify whether an IP gap exists in ICT and engineering PCTs and collaborate with other top-tier universities to implement programmes to support women inventors.	Direct Medium-term
Horizon Europe/FP10 European IP helpdesk	P3.3 Offer structured support for understanding publication vs. PCT trade-offs and equitable ownership for women researchers in ICT and engineering disciplines.	Direct Medium-term

Action 4. Guarantee sustainable returns for public money

Women founders are not inherently less investable than men founders. However, they often encounter barriers that can impede their access to capital and resources. The data show that women-led companies who overcome these barriers can outperform companies not led by women. The weight of the public purse can and should be used to level the playing field. The EIF has already launched the Gender Smart Equity Investment Programme to promote women leaders in venture capital and private equity.⁷⁰ It could require funds seeking co-investment partners to demonstrate how they intend to increase women's participation in investment decisions and benchmark their progress against the key metrics in GENDEX Pulse.

Other actions could include the following:

- Training investors and providing technological tools to enable them to identify and eliminate bias

⁶⁹ <https://www.westerndigital.com/en-ap/company/corporate-responsibility/people/diversity-inclusion#:~:text=She%20Invents%20is%20an%20internal%20program%20launched%20to,technical%20staff%20to%20support%20women%20and%20underrepresented%20inventors.>

⁷⁰ https://www.eif.org/what_we_do/equity/news/2024/eif-launches-gender-smart-equity-investment-programme.htm

- Expanding networking opportunities for women founders with potential investors, mentors and industry partners
- Expanding targeted mentorship and coaching programs for women founders in the wake of EIC’s Women Tech EU⁷¹ and Women Leadership Programme⁷²

Lead actor	Action	Impact
EIC	<p>P4.1 Establish a GENDEX investor club or label with training to identify and address bias; this should be mandatory for any fund receiving public co-investment.</p> <p>P4.2 Collaborate with member states to include this requirement for co-investment by any national or regional fund or funds.</p> <p>P4.3 For funds seeking public money, tie subsequent tranches to demonstrated progress in recruiting/retaining women-led investments.</p>	Direct Short-term
EIC partners	P4.4 Organise training and tools for the investor community.	Indirect Short-term
EIC and partners	P4.5 Scale up mentorship for potential women founders or co-founders in deep tech companies.	Direct Short-term

4.2.2 Why are the findings relevant for investors?

There is no inherent difference in the investability of women and men founders. However, women frequently encounter obstacles that limit their access to funding and support. Failure to address bias, conscious or otherwise, could cause VCs and their portfolio companies to miss out on financial returns and market opportunities. The data, both quantitative and qualitative, confirm that women seeking investment are treated differently from men. The available data also show that returns on IPOs and non-IPO exits are higher for women-led companies.

Action 1. Eliminate bias

The data show that biases (conscious or unconscious) exist within investment teams. Structured assessments can be used to evaluate the potential of companies, going beyond

⁷¹ Women TechEU - European Commission (https://eisma.ec.europa.eu/programmes/european-innovation-ecosystems/womentecheu_en#:~:text=Funded%20under%20the%20European%20Innovation%20Ecosystems%20work%20programme,help%20take%20their%20business%20to%20the%20next%20level.)

⁷² EIC Women Leadership Programme: empowering European women innovators | EIC Community (<https://eic.eisma.eu/community/stories/eic-women-leadership-programme-empowering-european-women-innovators#:~:text=The%20EIC%20Women%20Leadership%20Programme%20is%20a%20key,programme%20is%20set%20to%20transform%20Europe%E2%80%99s%20innovation%20landscape.>)

traditional metrics that may overlook different strengths; for example, some VCs take into account the possible undervaluation of women and the overvaluation of men.

Implementing blind review processes for investment proposals can effectively reduce gender bias by focusing solely on the merits of the proposal rather than the identity of the proposers. In addition, defining clear and structured evaluation processes will help to prevent similarity biases that can occur when investors favour start-ups that resemble successful past investments or their own backgrounds.

Lead actor	Action	Impact
VC firms	I1.1 Trial blind evaluations in a small subset of VCs; track the proportion of women at each stage to identify possible bias.	Indirect Medium-term
EIC	I1.2 Provide training in negotiation techniques, as well as templates to help women founders understand the 'standard' in investment terms and recognise when terms are lower.	Direct Short-term

Action 2. Seek diversity in investment committees

Diversity in investment committees is critical to broadening perspectives and improving decision-making. Including more women investors on teams increases the likelihood of challenging prevailing norms and uncovering valuable opportunities that might otherwise be overlooked.

Lead actor	Action	Impact
LPs	I2.1 Large limited partners (LPs), including pension funds and the EIF, can insist on a minimum threshold of women decision-makers in ICs.	Indirect Medium-term
VCs	I2.2 Retain and promote junior women investors to decision-making roles, supported by structured mentorship and management training.	Indirect Long-term

Action 3. If you see bias, call it out

Finally, the interviews with women founders revealed many instances in which they had been treated differently from their men counterparts. It is up to all actors in the entrepreneurial ecosystem to actively highlight and challenge discriminatory practices when they observe them.

Lead actor	Action	Impact
EIC	I3.1 Provide safe channels for founders and team members to report bias incidents	Indirect Medium-term

EIC	I3.2 Secure commitment from leading VC associations (e.g., Invest Europe or the European Private Equity and Venture Capital Association) to publicly endorse guidelines on the equitable treatment of founders	Indirect Medium-term
-----	--	------------------------

4.3 What's next?

4.3.1. Data to stimulate change

The scope of GENDEX within the proposed interventions is to provide data-driven guidelines, enriched with qualitative insights, to drive meaningful change. For instance, primary research activities (e.g., the GENDEX survey) have helped to capture key trends where secondary data are still lacking.

In addition to this report, the publication of interactive dashboards on the GENDEX website is key to providing an interactive view of the data collected for the index. Online dashboards make the Gender & Diversity Index accessible to a wider audience, including policymakers, investors and the general public. This promotes transparency and encourages broader engagement with the issue of gender diversity in deep tech. By providing easy access to relevant data, the dashboards empower stakeholders to make informed decisions and take action to promote gender diversity. For example, investors can use dashboards to identify and support women-led companies in deep tech, while policymakers can use them to monitor and track the current scenario.

As part of this pilot, GENDEX has developed GENDEX Pulse, an online tool designed to measure the performance of investors' portfolios against real benchmarks in terms of gender diversity, thanks to the online visual representation of the index provided by the dashboards.

More specifically, GENDEX Pulse aims to do the following:

For venture capitalists (VCs):

- Validate portfolio results and benchmarks concerning gender diversity in deep tech
- Attract better deal flow
- Showcase first-mover position
- Source pathways to increase performance

For LPs and public investors:

- Harmonize reporting and performance
- Compare funds to real benchmarks in terms of gender diversity in deep tech
- Source best practices
- Back investment decisions with a trusted 'GENDEX seal'

The role of GENDEX Pulse is also to use the Gender & Diversity Index, not only as a core benchmarking tool for investors to assess and track diversity in their portfolios but also for GENDEX to collect additional data that is not readily available from secondary sources (e.g.,

the number of female analysts in investment firms) directly from the original source on a voluntary basis. Through these efforts, the GENDEX pilot is moving from awareness to adoption, ensuring that diversity metrics become a standard consideration in venture capital workflows, policy-making and investor reporting frameworks.

To ensure the long-term adoption and sustainability of both the index and GENDEX Pulse, GENDEX will implement a structured exploitation plan focused on three key areas: **stakeholder engagement**, **data refinement** and **long-term visibility**. D4.5 Exploitation, Sustainability and Recommendations provides a comprehensive overview of how GENDEX will build on the Gender & Diversity Index and GENDEX Pulse to introduce data-driven diversity benchmarking and industry-wide adoption in the innovation ecosystem, spanning three timeframes: post-launch adoption (0-6 months), scaling industry adoption (6-18 months) and long-term sustainability (18+ months).

4.3.2 Future actions to improve the index

GENDEX aims to use data and qualitative insights to inform interventions that drive meaningful change. However, it also emphasises that increasing the number of women-led companies and improving reporting practices are essential for enhancing the quality and depth of data analysis. As noted in the previous section, initiatives such as GENDEX Pulse (developed as part of the GENDEX pilot) can help bridge these data gaps. Establishing a long-term continuous data collection framework would enable trend analysis, benchmarking and investor education, ultimately improving decision-making in the ecosystem.

Future research could also explore the relationship between diversity and sustainable financial performance in start-ups and scale-ups.

The GENDEX pilot focuses specifically on gender diversity and inclusion within the European innovation ecosystem, a priority validated by the EIC during the initial phases of the project. While this first initiative prioritises gender diversity in terms in scope and depth, the GENDEX team fully recognises the importance of addressing diversity in all its forms. It is clear that the future health and competitiveness of the European innovation ecosystem requires a broader look at diversity. Due to the practical constraints of this pilot, some limitations were necessary. The scope of future collaborations with the EIC could include further elements of diversity, such as ethnicity or migration status, although many founder characteristics generally considered to be indicators of diversity will be context-dependent, as noted in D 1.1 Review of the State of the Art.

Further research can explore the link between diversity and sustainable financial performance over a given period (e.g., five years).

4.4 Acknowledgements

We at GENDEX would like to express our sincere gratitude to all participants in primary research activities, who generously contributed their time and insights to this research. The valuable data and perspectives shared through surveys and interviews were crucial to this project. Due to the sensitive nature of some of the information gathered and to ensure participant confidentiality, all individual contributions remain anonymous. The insights gained from these contributions have significantly enriched this research and provided valuable insights into data collection and analysis.

We would like to extend our sincere gratitude to the esteemed members of the Board of Experts for their invaluable contributions to this project. Their expertise and insights, generously shared at Board of Experts meetings, have been instrumental in shaping the direction and enhancing the rigour of this project. The authors are deeply appreciative of their time, guidance and support:

Paula Aitkenhead, Susana de Antonio, Kat Borlongan, Raph Crouan, Magdalena Cymerys, Shiva Dustdar, Michael Jackson, Dr Albena Kuyumdzhieva, Mary McKenna, Valentina Milanova and Sami Moughrabie

[BOARD OF EXPERTS - GENDEX](https://eurogendex.org/board-of-experts/) (https://eurogendex.org/board-of-experts/)

ANNEX 1 METHODOLOGY AND LIMITATIONS

As noted, the Gender & Diversity Index used multiple sources and data collection methods, relying mainly on secondary sources, and on primary sources where evident data gaps in terms of availability were recorded. The Gender & Diversity Index employs a mixed-methods approach to investigate the gender diversity in deep tech in the European Union member states and UK. Quantitative analyses are complemented by qualitative insights, to provide context and explore the underlying factors influencing the quantitative findings.

Limitations related to data availability and potential biases are acknowledged and addressed throughout the report and in this section. Analysing deep tech founders, start-ups, scale-ups and investors for this project presented data challenges. Reliable, representative and regularly updated information is limited in certain areas for pre-seed and seed investment rounds. This data scarcity is a key constraint for deep tech company analysis in general, and particularly for women-led companies.

Unlike public companies, standardized reporting formats and schedules are lacking. Furthermore, deep tech enterprises make up a small portion of all European businesses, and women-led companies comprise an even smaller fraction of that subset. Where possible, multiple secondary sources were used for the Gender & Diversity Index to bolster the data sample's representativeness.

Despite the use of valid primary and secondary sources, the process of collecting and analysing the data for the development of the index was subject to a number of limitations, as for any research activity.

A summary of the methodology and main limitations related to each data source is presented in this section, divided by tier. The following section also lists the key definitions on which the index is based and which are referred to several times throughout the analysis of the metrics in this document.

4.5 Key definitions

Within the development of the index and for the purpose of data collection, the following necessary definitions are provided. This is the final list of definitions used to define, populate and analyse the index:

- **Deep tech:** Technologies categorised within the scope fields established by the European Innovation Council⁷³
- **Women-led company:** Company with at least one woman in a key executive or board member position.

⁷³ European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, The European Innovation Council – Impact report 2023 – Accelerating Deep Tech in Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/072707>

- Comment: An ideal definition would include the equity ownership relative to other founders (accounting for dilution) of women; however, the data are not readily available from current sources. Furthermore, the common practice in some EU countries is not have individual shareholdings but holding companies and vehicles, which further complicates the processes. Additionally, the GENDEX Board of Experts noted that board membership is considered an integral and important part of governance.
- The Dealroom database provides a static view of team members that does change over time for C-levels/board members. Due to this limitation, the definition of "women-led" was adjusted to include active women founders/co-founders in the period observed for the Dealroom data set, and this is reflected in indicators relying on the Dealroom database only⁷⁴.
- **Unicorn:** Privately held start-ups valued at over \$1 billion, often mature enough for IPOs or significant acquisition events
 - Comment: The common definition requires the value to be given in USD rather than EUR.
- **Top-tier tech companies:** Companies included in the Magnificent 7⁷⁵, identified European tech unicorns and European technology companies with a market cap >€30 billion in 2024
 - Comment: The definition of top-tier tech companies is related to desk research to be performed. For this reason, the number of EU unicorns is to be limited to the top 10 tech and deep tech companies by last available valuation in 2024.
- **Top-performing research institutions:** Research institutions, both universities and RTOs, in the EU that have the highest number of patents conceded over the previous 10-year period.
 - Comment: The particular operational model for RTOs presents a difficulty in measuring performance through commonly applied metrics such as publications, spin-offs created, clinical trials or public funding received. The commercial research nature means high-performance from adoption by clients and partners may not be captured. However, the number of contributions to open-source databases as an additional approach to the number of patents to define RTO performance (as presented in D1.2 Gender & Diversity Scorecard) has to be discarded because of the high dispersion of databases to which RTOs contribute in different fields, providing only a partial and unreliable view for this metric.
- **Top-tier institutions:** Research performing universities in Europe that produce the greatest spin-out value as defined in the *European Deep Tech Report 2023*⁷⁶
 - Comment: Calculations were performed on the product of the amount of spin-outs per institution by a score for stage from seed investment to established unicorn. Limitations are present due to the difference of participation of universities in ventures between member states.

⁷⁴ Check Appendix A, Methodology and Limitations

⁷⁵ Refers to the commonly described term for influential US technology giants: Apple (AAPL), Microsoft (MSFT), Alphabet (GOOGL), Amazon (AMZN) Meta Platforms (META), Tesla (TSLA), NVIDIA (NVDA)

⁷⁶ Source: THE 2023 EUROPEAN DEEP TECH REPORT (2023), Dealroom: [The European Deep Tech Report 2023 | Dealroom.co](https://www.dealroom.co/insights/european-deep-tech-report-2023)

4.6 Analysis through secondary sources

The construction of the index relies on a set of externally collected databases. The final list for the construction of the index includes:

- Statistical data sets:
 - Sources : Eurostat, OECD, PATSTAT (EPO)
- Specialised company database providers:
 - Sources: Pitchbook, Dealroom
- Desk research
 - Compilation of data through reviews of annual reports, websites and other sources of information for companies and individuals, including professional social media networks (LinkedIn)

Deep tech talent tier: Eurostat and OECD

- **Methodology:** Data sets sourced from Eurostat and the OECD were utilized for the analysis of the deep tech talent tier (see graphs for source details).
- **Limitations:** These data sets have a time lag between the date of data collection and accessibility, ranging from 12 to 24 months until 2024, in line with the data collection periods set by both providers. This has led to the necessary limitation of the analysis to the period 2017-2022 only. Additionally, the presence of missing values for certain country divisions limits the ability to conduct a more comprehensive geographical analysis for certain data points.

Deep tech talent tier: Defining the share of women leaders in STEM in top-tier institutions

- **Methodology:** To ascertain the proportion of women chairs in STEM disciplines at leading institutions, data were gathered from annual diversity and inclusion reports, as well as institutional websites. Data collection focused exclusively on the designated leading European institutions, ranked by spin-out value according to Dealroom's *European Deep Tech Report, 2023*. Data verification was carried out directly by the university diversity teams in all cases except Cambridge University.
- **Limitations:** Access to staff lists at Cambridge is restricted for non-faculty members, so the data are an estimate derived from previous reports and the institution's overall diversity and inclusion reporting.

Intellectual and social capital tier: Defining the share of women employed in top-tier tech companies

- **Methodology:** To be able to analyse the top tech companies, the structure of this metric was first defined. Current market capitalisation was used to identify the top-performing organisations in three groups of tech companies – European tech companies, the global Magnificent 7 and European tech unicorns – to cover the deep tech space in a holistic manner. For desk research, reviewing annual integrated and sustainability reports was the preferred source of data, but this was not available for all companies. Where data were not publicly reported, they were estimated from a list of employees present on LinkedIn and then gendered using employee names with a

dedicated software tool.⁷⁷ Professional networks (e.g., LinkedIn) are an accessible tool for tracking trends in the proportion of female employees in a company and were used to complement the analysis of the proportion of women employed in top tech companies.

- **Limitations:** Both types of data source have limitations. In the case of annual reports and institutional websites, there is no fully standardised way of reporting diversity metrics, particularly from a regional perspective. Top technology companies do not report on the gender breakdown of their workforce in the same structure, detail or geographical scope; some do not report at all. The geographical perimeter is usually global for most of the world's top tech companies in terms of the gender breakdown of their workforce. Estimates are needed for European figures. Data samples from LinkedIn can provide a trend (a snapshot of the workforce) but are not intended to reflect the true gender composition of the workforce at missing companies. The average sample of profiles visible from LinkedIn for a given company is around 1,000. The genderisation of names has a limited margin of error, depending on the nature of the name and the cultural context. The current timeframe for the LinkedIn data is 2024 only, as the data collection is static.

Intellectual and social capital tier: Defining the share of women employed in top-tier RTOs and women inventorship

- **Methodology:** The EPO's PATSTAT is important for patent intelligence and statistics, but it does not provide a gender breakdown. First, the list of inventors over a period of time (primary data set) has to be extracted from PATSTAT using an SQL query. In order to determine the proportion of PTCs with at least one woman inventor in the inventors' team, the names of the applicants had to be gendered. The primary data set was downloaded from PASTAT according to the following structure: PTC ID, inventor name and country of residence, PTC publication date for granted patents (final stage of the process). The data set was cleaned and prepared for name-to-gender classification based on inventor name, then the online tool Genderize.io was used to infer the gender of the applicant, as with the LinkedIn profiles used to determine the proportion of women employed in top technology companies.
- **Limitations:** The process of registering a patent is complex, consisting of stages spread over several years until a patent is granted. The registration of a patent in all European countries adds to the complexity in terms of the number of records of a patent, and an inventor may have several records for the same registration in the PATSTAT database. Therefore, extracting the correct and relevant record can be challenging. There is an additional margin of error due to human factor limitations when entering data into a PTC application (e.g., transposing first and last names). Approximately 5% of the raw data sample had to be excluded from the data set.

Investment and social capital tier and asset and investment tier: Data availability and data integration from company databases

- **Methodology:** The Pitchbook and Dealroom databases were used to define the data sets for all indicators relevant to identifying and analysing the presence and

⁷⁷ For more details on the software tool, Genderize.io, and name-to-gender classification methods, please see: [The Use of Gender Classification in Academic Research](#)

performance of women-led deep tech companies in scope to maximise coverage over time and countries in scope.

The geographical coverage for both databases (company headquarters) is the member states of the European Union and the United Kingdom.

For each technology area, country and deal stage, Pitchbook provided corresponding data for women-led and men-led companies, as this data can only be retrieved from the backend of the platform.

The PitchBook data set was defined using multiple tags and keywords for each area to represent the technology areas in scope (Table 3).

Table 3. Technology areas populated from PitchBook

Tech Area	Dealroom Tags
Advanced connectivity, navigation and digital technologies	<p><i>Keywords:</i> Advanced connectivity, navigation systems, 5G technology, 6G technology, edge computing</p> <p><i>Verticals:</i> Agtech, augmented reality, big data, cleantech, climatetech, blockchain, cybersecurity, Internet of Things, mobility tech, virtual reality</p>
Advanced materials, manufacturing and recycling technologies	<p><i>Keywords:</i> Advanced materials, recycling technologies, recycling materials, sustainable materials, smart materials, smart materials technology, 3D printing materials, 4D printing materials, architected hierarchical materials, structural materials, thermal materials, advanced alloys, advanced polymer materials, advanced battery materials, digital fabrication, composite materials, metamaterials-based technology, polymers based products, plastic polymers, natural fibers</p>
Advanced sensing technologies	<p><i>Keywords:</i> Advanced sensing technologies, advanced sensing materials, fiber optic sensors, fiber optics sensing system, advanced sensor, infrared sensor, sensing technologies, gas sensor technology gas sensor system, acoustic sensor, acoustic sensing, optical sensor, optical sensing system, advanced semiconductors, semiconductor, optical sensor, optical sensing system, edge technology, sensor technology</p>
Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies	<p><i>Verticals:</i> Artificial intelligence and machine learning</p> <p><i>Emerging spaces:</i> Information technology > Swarm AI; Information technology > generative AI</p>
Biotechnologies	<p><i>Industries:</i> Healthcare > pharmaceuticals and biotechnology > biotechnology</p> <p><i>Verticals:</i> Life sciences</p>

	<i>Keywords:</i> Synthetic biology, novel manufacturing, pharmaceutical processing, cell and gene therapy, omics, genetics
Energy technologies	Industries: Energy Emerging spaces: Energy <i>Keywords:</i> bioenergy, energy generation, renewable energy generation, geothermal energy, energy conversion, energy transmission, power grid, green hydrogen, hydrogen, hydrogen fuel, hydrogen fuel systems, nuclear power, nuclear energy, ocean energy, alternative fuel, solar technology, wind technology, energy storage batteries
Quantum technologies	<i>Emerging spaces:</i> Information technology > quantum sensing; information technology > quantum computing <i>Keywords:</i> Quantum sensing
Robotics & autonomous systems	Vertical: Robotics and drones Vertical: Autonomous cars <i>Emerging space:</i> Autonomous delivery <i>Emerging space:</i> Autonomous vehicle simulation
Space and propulsion technologies	<i>Keywords:</i> Space propulsion technologies, in-space propulsion, space vehicles, deep space communication, spacecraft systems, space traffic management, propulsion systems, earthling observation, meteorology, space debris, space situational awareness, spacecraft technologies, space satellites <i>Emerging spaces:</i> Business Products and Services (B2B) > Small Satellites

The output of the PitchBook search query consists of approximately 20,000 companies.

For Dealroom, a full data set was downloaded using the following search query:

- Age: Companies founded since 1990
- HQ region: European Union + UK
- Technologies: Deep tech
- Excluding: Outside tech tags

The Dealroom data set by technology area was then defined by assigning a technology area based on the tag classification provided by Dealroom ([Table 4](#)).

Table 4. Technology areas population from Dealroom

Tech Area	Dealroom Tags
Advanced connectivity, navigation and digital technologies	Internet of things, IoT, lot, blockchain, agritech, augmented reality, virtual reality, big data, edge, edge computing, mobility, connectivity, cybersecurity, agtech, security, analytics, predictive analytics, industrial IoT, 5G, 6G, navigation and mapping, supply chain management, geopositioning, connected device
Advanced materials, manufacturing and recycling technologies	Advanced materials, nanotechnology, 3D printing, additive manufacturing, circular economy, recycling, smart materials, carbon removal, carbon capture, carbon storage, novel materials, nanomaterials, nanotech, simulation tech, climate tech, engineering and manufacturing equipment, shape-memory alloys, urban tech, prototype
Advanced sensing technologies	Lidar, fiberoptic, fiber optic, advanced semiconductors, sensor tech, sensor, semiconductor, laser, photonic, haptic technology, haptic, optical technology
Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies	Artificial intelligence, GenAI, machine learning, NLP, natural language processing, generative AI, AI application
Biotechnologies	Biotechnology, biotech, genetics, genomics, stem cells, gene therapy, synthetic biology, techbio drug discovery, drug discovery, biochemicals, foodtech, medtech, health tech, health
Energy technologies	Energy, stationary storage, thermal energy storage, thermal, long duration energy storage, electric vehicle battery, EV battery, hydrogen, solar, solar power, alternative fuel, greentech
Quantum technologies	Quantum, quantum technology
Robotics and autonomous systems	Robotic, autonomous, exoskeleton, autonomous systems, autonomous mobility, drones, robotics, robot, rehabilitation
Space and propulsion technologies	Aerospace, space tech, space, space upstream, launch vehicles, space transportation, ESA, space DTI, aviation, satellite, nanosatellite

Companies from the Dealroom data set that did not belong to the technology areas in scope were subsequently deleted, resulting in a total number of approximately 8,000 companies in scope.

To standardise values, all deals and valuations that were not expressed in euros were converted from the original currency to euros using constant annual exchange rates for the reference year.

Database matching was then required. After reviewing the PitchBook sample, between 25% and 30% of the companies were estimated not to be fully aligned with the deep tech technologies in the project scope, for example for artificial intelligence technology areas and having a SaaS product offering based on AI for human resource management, as well as those not strictly related to AI R&D, such as large language models or Swarm AI. At the same time, although generally reliable, it missed some companies that should be considered as deep tech based on the scope of the project. For these reasons, indicators using both data sets are calculated using a weighted averaging methodology that values the higher data quality of the Dealroom data set and the broader coverage of PitchBook.

- **Limitations:** Ensuring data accuracy and consistency across both platforms can be complex. The classification of each technology field in both data sets should be done manually. Both data sets may still omit a limited number of companies relevant to the reference fields. Given the large number of companies analysed, companies may instead belong to more than one technology area due to their offering, which may lead to double counting for the technology area split (as highlighted in the source notes in D3.2 Validated Gender & Diversity Index Scorecard). The two databases also use different taxonomy classifications, which poses a challenge to the convergence of the two data sets. For example, the Pitchbook classification was used for the deal stage breakdown and then applied to the Dealroom data set. There may be small margins or errors in the reconciliation process. Dealroom also provides a static view of team members, which changes over time for C-level/board members. Due to this limitation, the definition of women-led has been adjusted to active women founders/co-founders over the period observed for the Dealroom data set, and this is reflected in indicators that rely solely on the Dealroom database – AI2a Number of IPOs of women-led companies, AI2b Number of exits by women founders (non-IPO), AI2c Valuation of exits by women founders (non-IPO), AI2d Valuation on IPO of women-led companies, AI3a Number of women-led companies valued at over \$1 billion, and AI3b Time to reach unicorn classification.

This element was also taken into account when evaluating the weighted average methodology.

As PitchBook does not allow publication of low absolute numbers, for indicators that rely on absolute numbers (e.g., unicorns and number of IPOs), only the Dealroom data set is used to comply with PitchBook's publication guidelines.

Deal and company value reporting is often inconsistent, resulting in missing records for certain indicators (e.g., missing deal value, missing company valuation and missing deal classification) or some discrepancies between metrics showing the total absolute number of deals and total values expressed in millions of euro. In addition, for small countries such as Malta, Cyprus and Latvia, the number of companies covered by available data is often low, especially for women-led companies. For the same reason, the data sets may have limited data availability for selected data breakdowns, as

highlighted in purple in D3.2 Validated Gender & Diversity Index Scorecard, where full data tables for the Index are provided.

As Pitchbook does not track enough EIC beneficiaries, only the Dealroom data set is used to provide the data split between EIC and non-EIC beneficiaries. Due to this lack of data availability, the EIC vs. non-EIC data split is presented as an additional view to the company-related indicators to show a trend in the tables presented in D3.2 Validated Gender & Diversity Index Scorecard but should not be considered as complete and representative of the entire EIC universe.

Investor tier

- **Methodology:** The full investor tier is based on Pitchbook data only, as it provides full coverage of investors directly investing in deep tech companies of any size, from key decision-makers to angel investors and, most importantly, fund AUM. The tier considers venture capital (VC), private equity (PE), family office and angel investors – the latter only for metric 11b. The investors considered should have a European focus and have made deals in the sample considered.
- **Limitations:** The availability of a single database may limit the representativeness and reliability of the results, even if the samples are statistically relevant.

Impact tier: Limitations for reliable conclusions

- **Limitations:** Drawing definitive conclusions about the impact of women in the European innovation ecosystem is hampered by a lack of data availability. The low presence of women-led companies makes it incredibly difficult to determine the correlation between the presence of women and actual performance outcomes. Although some evidence can be drawn on the superior performance of women-led companies in IPOs and exits ⁷⁸, other key performance indicators (e.g., the internal rate of return [IRR] of VC funds) currently pose significant challenges in terms of data availability. The private nature of VC investment and the competitive landscape often discourage the publication of detailed performance data, such as fund-level IRRs. This lack of transparency hampers the ability to benchmark investment performance in terms of gender representation at the portfolio level in the deep tech sector. The absence of standardized revenue reporting for start-ups, particularly in the early stages, presents a significant challenge in accurately assessing whether women-led companies have delivered a superior performance.

The lack of data availability highlights the need to improve data reporting even more, including for the purpose of robust quantitative data analysis and correlation.

4.7 Analysis on primary sources

GENDEX survey

- **Methodology:** The draft Gender & Diversity Index 2.0 includes data from the GENDEX Survey (September 2024) for team workforce composition, IP ownership and vesting schedules. D2.2 Quantitative Survey Results provides full survey results, including information focusing on diverse aspects such as gender, ethnicity, educational

⁷⁸ See the Asset and investment capital tier for related metrics

background, migration status, work experience and serial entrepreneurship tendencies for women and men deep tech founder and co-founders in the EU27 and UK. The survey was conducted between July and September 2024. Respondents had to meet the following screening criteria to proceed with the questionnaire:

- The respondent should be a founder or co-founder of a start-up or scale-up.
- The company's offering should be in one of the technology areas covered by the EIC (see the paragraph on key definitions above)
- The company's current headquarters should be located in one of the EU27 member states and the United Kingdom or should be established in the future.

The survey methods were both computer-assisted web interviewing (CATI) and computer-assisted telephone interviewing (CAWI), following an online link to the questionnaire (the full questionnaire is available in Annex 2 of this document). Responses were collected without any direct or possible association with any organisation and were reviewed in aggregate form.

- **Limitations:** The GENDEX survey provides a sample of 150 deep tech founders and co-founders across the 27 member states of the European Union, which is statistically relevant and provides a trend, but is not intended to be representative of the entire European landscape. Country and technology area breakdowns are not provided for indicators based on survey data, as the sample is not sufficiently consistent. Start-ups and scale-ups founders, similarly but even more so other technology leaders, are a difficult target for primary research activities as they face time pressures combined with numerous survey requests, often leading to survey fatigue. In addition, men founders in particular may perceive gender diversity as a secondary concern compared to technical milestones or fundraising, leading to lower prioritisation and therefore less engagement with related requests.

As this is the first year of the survey, the current timeframe for survey-based indicators is 2024 only.

Note: Respondents are referred to as men and women founders and co-founders, which differs from GENDEX's definition of women-led businesses, as the questionnaire was defined and the survey carried out in the field before the final definition was revised and approved by GENDEX's Board of Experts.

GENDEX interviews

- **Methodology:** The GENDEX interview series was conducted with a qualitative sample of 20 women founders and co-founders of deep tech start-ups and scale-ups, as well as venture capital investors. All interviews were conducted via online meetings and lasted a maximum of 45 minutes. Due to the sensitivity of the topic and to promote freedom of expression, each interviewee was guaranteed complete anonymity. All highlights and quotes within this report are presented anonymously so that they cannot be traced back to the interviewee in any way. The interviews provide anecdotal evidence of the gender gap in the European innovation ecosystem and are used to complement the analysis of metrics of the Gender & Diversity Index (full interview guide is available in Annex 2 of this document).⁷⁹

⁷⁹ Full summary of GENDEX interviews is available in Deliverable 2.3 Qualitative Interviews results

- **Limitations:** The number of people interviewed, and the inherent limitations of qualitative research, make the findings relevant as a complement to primary and secondary quantitative analysis, but not easily generalisable to larger populations.

ANNEX 2 PRIMARY RESEARCH DATA COLLECTION TOOLS

Survey questionnaire

Introductory text

IDC, one of the world's leading technology research firms, together with BluSpecs and Founderland, is developing a Gender & Diversity Index (GENDEX) as a pilot initiative funded under the Horizon Europe programme. As part of the spectrum of actions under the European Innovation Council (EIC), GENDEX's mission is to bridge data gaps and enhance access to diverse talent within the innovation ecosystem. The aim of this survey is to collect relevant information on how diversity impacts the fundraising journey for start-up and scale-up founders and co-founders in the European innovation ecosystem.

The survey should take no more than 20 minutes to complete. Your answers will be kept confidential, will not be associated with you or your organisation, and will only be reviewed in aggregate form.

Opening survey screen

S01. Are you currently a founder or co-founder of a tech start-up or scale-up?

1. Yes
2. No [TERMINATE]

S02. Where did you first incorporate your company?

1. Austria
2. Belgium
3. Bulgaria
4. Croatia
5. Cyprus
6. Czech Republic
7. Denmark
8. Estonia
9. Finland
10. France
11. Germany
12. Greece
13. Hungary
14. Ireland
15. Italy
16. Latvia
17. Lithuania
18. Luxembourg

19. Malta
20. Netherlands
21. Poland
22. Portugal
23. Romania
24. Slovakia
25. Slovenia
26. Spain
27. Sweden
28. United Kingdom
29. Other (please, specify)

S03. [Only if replying Other to S02.] Was your company subsequently incorporated into one of the European Union members or UK?

1. Yes
2. No [TERMINATE]

S04. [Only if replying all except Other to S02.] Was your company subsequently incorporated into a country outside the European Union members or UK?

1. Yes [TERMINATE]
2. No

S05. Which of the following industry sectors best represents the principal business activity of your organization? In the case of multiple activities, choose the one that generates the highest revenue.

Please select one response

1. Advanced connectivity, navigation and digital technologies (e.g., 5G/6G, Security technologies, Internet of Things, Edge Computing, Augmented and Virtual Reality)
2. Advanced materials, manufacturing & recycling technologies (e.g., Nanomaterials, Smart Materials, Safe and Sustainable Materials)
3. Advanced sensing technologies (e.g., LIDAR, Fiber Optics sensors, Infrared sensors, Wearable Sensors)
4. Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies
5. Biotechnologies (genetics & synbio) (e.g., Cell and gene therapies, synthetic biology, novel manufacturing)

6. Energy technologies (e.g., Clean energy technologies, Energy storage technologies, Electric vehicles)
7. Quantum Technologies
8. Robotics & autonomous systems (e.g., Autonomous robots, Autonomous vehicles,
9. Space & propulsion technologies (e.g., Spacecraft and satellites, Deep space communication, In-Space propulsion, Support infrastructure)
10. Other [TERMINATE]

S06. Have you received any grant or direct investment from the European Innovation Council (EIC) in your current company? Refer to last funding option received

1. Yes, grants
2. Yes, direct investments
3. No

Founder background

Q01. Which gender do you identify with?

1. Woman
2. Man
3. Nonbinary
4. Prefer not to say
5. Other

Q02. In which country you were born? (*Open field*)

Q03. In which country are you currently resident?

Please select one response

1. Austria
2. Belgium
3. Bulgaria
4. Croatia
5. Cyprus
6. Czech Republic
7. Denmark
8. Estonia

9. Finland
10. France
11. Germany
12. Greece
13. Hungary
14. Ireland
15. Italy
16. Latvia
17. Lithuania
18. Luxembourg
19. Malta
20. Netherlands
21. Poland
22. Portugal
23. Romania
24. Slovakia
25. Slovenia
26. Spain
27. Sweden
28. United Kingdom
29. Other (please, specify)

Q04. Do you perceive yourself as diverse in your ecosystem in one or more the following categories?

Please select all that apply

1. Gender
2. Religion
3. Sexual orientation
4. Migration
5. Ethnicity
6. Socioeconomic status
7. Disability/neurodivergency
8. Other (please, specify)
9. None of the above

Q05. Which is your highest level of educational qualification?

Please select one

1. Doctoral Studies (PhD)
2. Master's Degree (MSC or MA), including Master of Business Administration (MBA)
3. Professional Masters
4. Bachelor's Degree
5. Other (please, specify)

Q06. At which institution did you attain your highest qualification? (*Open field*)

Q07. What did you study?

Please select one

1. Arts & Humanities (e.g., Art, Philosophy & History, Architecture)
2. Business & Economics (e.g., Business & Management, Accounting & Finance, Economics)
3. Clinical & Health (e.g., Medicine, Dentistry, other health subjects)
4. Computer Science
5. Education (e.g., Education, Teacher training)
6. Engineering
7. Law
8. Life Sciences (e.g., Biological Science, Agriculture & Forestry)
9. Physical Sciences (Mathematics and Statistics, Physics, Chemistry)
10. Psychology
11. Other (please, specify)
12. Social sciences (e.g., Communication & Media, Sociology)

Q08. Have you previously worked for any of the following before founding your own company?

Please select all that apply

1. Big Tech (e.g., Microsoft, Apple, Alphabet/Google, Amazon)
2. Big Pharma/Biomedical companies (e.g., Pfizer, Novartis, AstraZeneca, Roche)
3. University or research institution
4. Always been an entrepreneur
5. Other (please, specify)

Q09. Have you founded a company before your current one?

Please select one

1. No, this is my first company
2. One
3. From two to three
4. More than three
5. Other (please specify)

Decision to found

Q10. Were there any role models that inspired you to start your own company?

Please select one

1. Yes
2. No

Q11. [Only if replying Yes to Q10] What specific attributes of that /those role model(s) did you relate to? (*Open field*)

Q12. Which of your networks were most useful in finding the following:

Please select all that apply

Columns

1. Co-founders/team members
2. Customers
3. Investors

Rows

1. Personal networks (e.g., friends, family, personal acquaintances)
2. Previous business relationships (e.g., previous companies contacts and clients)
3. Investors network (e.g., Venture Capitals)
4. Dedicated online platforms (e.g., crowdfunding)
5. Events and conferences (e.g., pitch competitions, networking meetups)
6. Start-up communities (e.g., incubators/accelerators)
7. Referrals from other entrepreneurs
8. Advisors and mentors
9. Other (please specify)

Q13. What was your target revenue when you did your first pitch? (SOM in millions €) (*Open question*)

Q14. What is your target revenue now? (SOM in millions €) (*Open question*)

Q15. Do you personally own any (IPs)?

Please, select all that apply

1. Patents
2. Trademarks
3. Design
4. Copyrights
5. Digital assets
6. None [exclusive choice]
7. Other (please specify)

Q16. [Only if at least one of answer option in Q.14 is not None] Where did you develop your IP?

Please select all that apply

1. Previous or current company
2. Universities or research institutions
3. Independently
4. Other (please specify)

Q17. Did you feel you had the following skills when starting your own company?

Please select all that apply

1. Technical skills (Yes/No)
2. Entrepreneurial skills (Yes/No)

Company background and funding

If you have founded more than one company, please refer to the company where you are currently a founder or co-founder for the following section.

Q18. In which country is your company HQ located?

Please select one

1. Austria
2. Belgium
3. Bulgaria
4. Croatia
5. Cyprus
6. Czech Republic
7. Denmark

8. Estonia
9. Finland
10. France
11. Germany
12. Greece
13. Hungary
14. Ireland
15. Italy
16. Latvia
17. Lithuania
18. Luxembourg
19. Malta
20. Netherlands
21. Poland
22. Portugal
23. Romania
24. Slovakia
25. Slovenia
26. Spain
27. Sweden
28. United Kingdom

Q19. When was your company funded?

Please select one response

1. Less than one year ago
2. 1 to 2 years ago
3. 3 to 5 years ago
4. 6 to 10 years ago
5. More than 10 years ago

Q20. Please indicate an estimate (%) for the following:

Please choose one answer for each:

Columns

1. Less than 20%
2. 20% to 50%

3. More than 50%
4. 100%

Rows

1. % of women from the total workforce
2. % of women from company executives
3. % of women from the technical workforce
4. % of women Board Members

Q21. What was your last round of funding?

Please select one response

1. Angel
2. Pre-seed and Seed
3. Series A
4. Series B
5. Series C
6. Series D
7. Exit (IPO or M&A)
8. Other (please, specify)

Q22. How long did it take you to receive your first term sheet?

Please select one response

1. Less than 6 months
2. From 6 months to one year
3. From one year to three
4. More than three years

Q23. How much did you raise in your first round?

Please select one response

1. Up to half a million €
2. Half to 1 million €
3. 1 million to 2 million €
4. 2 to 5 million €
5. More than 5 million €

Q24. How long was your vesting schedule in your first raise?

Please select one response

1. 4-year vesting with a 1-year cliff
2. 3-year vesting with a 6-month cliff
3. 5-year vesting with no cliff
4. Prefer not to answer
5. Other (please, specify)

4.8 Interview guide for start-up and scale-up founders

Founder background

Let's start talking about you as a founder:

1. Do you perceive yourself as being part of a minority in your ecosystem?
2. If yes, have you ever felt that you have been treated differently to other founders based on your element of diversity? In what occasions?
3. Tell me more about your background:
 - a. In which country you were born?
 - b. Which university you have attended and what is your highest level of education?
 - c. Did you need to move from your country of birth to study, or to found and grow your own company? If yes, why?
 - d. Where did you work prior to founding your own company?
4. Tell me about your decision to found your company:
 - a. What inspired you?
 - b. Who were your role models, if any?
 - c. What problems did you expect to encounter? What problems did you encounter?
 - d. Do you think other founders experienced the same problems?

Fundraising journey

Let's consider now the fundraising journey for your own company:

1. Why did you decide to seek external funding for your company? At what phase of development of your journey?
2. Can you describe your initial challenges in fundraising?
 - a. If you had more than one round, does raising get easier after the first round? If yes, why?
3. What networks and contacts were you able to leverage to fundraise/grow your company?
4. Did you feel you were competing with others not on an equal footing? If yes, why?
5. Did you feel you were penalised compared to peers on your first raise? (*e.g., time to raise, cap tables, vesting schedules, raise amount*)
6. In general terms, what do you know now that you have wished to know before starting your fundraising journey?

4.9 Interview guide for investors

Investor background

Let's start talking about you as an investor:

1. Just for context, could you tell us:
 - a. The AUM of your firm
 - b. The type of companies you invest in (probe for stage, probe for deep tech)
 - c. Where do you invest (national, European, global remit)
 - d. Whether you were involved in raising the fund (if so, how many funds have you raised)

2. Tell me a little bit about yourself:
 - a. Which university did you attend and what is your highest level of education?
 - b. Where did you work prior to start your career as an investor? Did you have any role models?

3. Tell us about how your career has progressed? Have you encountered any obstacles in reaching your full potential? Have you ever felt you needed to make different personal, or career decisions compared to your peers?

4. Do you perceive yourself as being part of a minority in your ecosystem? If yes, have you ever felt that you have been treated differently to other investors based on your element of diversity? If yes, do you think this has ever impacted your career?

Funding pipeline

Let's now talk about your investment decisions:

1. Is diversity important for your fund? If so, why?
2. Do you have any policies regarding diversity that you apply in making investment decisions?
3. Do you check for bias in your investment decision making process? How?
4. Do your LPs ask about diversity in your portfolio?
5. Do your LPs require you to report on diversity metrics?
6. What is the one single thing you believe would eliminate bias in the investor ecosystem?

ANNEX 3 PRESENTATION ON KEY GENDEX HYPOTHESIS AND DATA HIGHLIGHTS

D3.3 GENDEX Data Analysis of the Gender & Diversity Index

Key GENDEX Hypothesis and Data Highlights- February 2025

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or (none of the granting authority). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

About GENDEX

- 1** GENDEX aimed to create a comprehensive and actionable Gender & Diversity index for the European innovation landscape, addressing significant gender disparities in leadership positions and investment sectors across the deeptech ecosystem.
- 2** By providing detailed data on gender, GENDEX sought to empower investors and policymakers to make informed decisions that enhance diversity and inclusion within their organisations and investments.
- 3** The Gender & Diversity Index aimed to identify gender diversity and inclusion gaps in the European innovation and entrepreneurship landscape, specifically in Deep Tech areas of interest for the European Innovation Council (EIC).

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

GEN The EIC

1

The European Innovation Council (EIC) is a flagship initiative of the European Union designed to identify and support breakthrough technologies and gamechanging innovations.

2

In 2023, the EIC Fund, the investment arm of the EIC concluded over 100 investments in Deep Tech companies worth around €1.2 billion. The total value of the overall portfolio of EIC supported companies, including those from the pilot and predecessor, is almost €70 billion.

DEX

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

Foundational Hypothesis of GENDEX

1

There is a lack of diversity in the Deep Tech sectors within the scope of the EIC

2

The lack of diversity at the investment stage stems from a lack of diversity at the earlier stages of the pipeline

3

Even when investment is secured, women receive terms that are less favourable than those offered to men

4

The investment gap between women and men highlights an opportunity to expand the pool of deep tech founders

4

Full data analysis and commentary available in Deliverable 3.3 Data Analysis of the Gender & Diversity Index final report

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

GENDEX's Foundational Hypothesis

- 1 There is a lack of diversity in the Deep Tech sectors within the scope of the EIC
- 2 The lack of diversity at the investment stage stems from a lack of diversity at the earlier stages of the pipeline
- 3 Even when investment is secured, women receive terms that are less favourable than those offered to men.
- 4 The investment gap between women and men highlights an opportunity to expand the pool of deep tech founders.

5

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

1 There is a lack of diversity in the Deep Tech sectors within the scope of the EIC

Significant gender diversity gap in Deep Tech women-led companies

22%

Women-led companies in EU27+UK (2014-2024 average)

Countries

28%

Sweden (2024)

12%

Croatia (2024)

Sectors

35%

Biotechnologies (2024)

10%

Space & Propulsion Tech (2024)

Significant gender diversity gap in the workforce composition of Deep Tech companies

Share (%) of Women - Total Workforce

6

Source: GENDEX analysis on a sample of a total EU+UK of around N=20,000 companies from PitchBook and N=around 8,000 companies Dealroom

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

Source: GENDEX Survey, August 2024, N=51 women founders in EU+UK; N= 98 men founders in EU+UK

1

There is a lack of diversity in the Deep Tech sectors within the scope of the EIC

Significant gender diversity gap in the investor ecosystem providing funds to Deep Tech companies

Less women investors

13% Funds (VCs, PEs and Family Offices) with at least one-woman investor in a key decision-making role (2014-2024 average)

Source: PitchBook, November 2024. Total decision maker investors with an entity in EU+UK that have invested in EU+UK DeepTech companies. Total N=2,139 in VC Firms; Total N= 463 in PE firms; Total N= 68 in Family Offices

Less women angels

7% Women business angels investing in Deep Tech companies (2014-2024 average)

Source: PitchBook, October 2024, N=around 2,000 EU+UK angel investors that have invested in EU+UK Deep Tech companies

Less funding to women-led companies

31% of investments from VC, PE, and family office investments with a European remit went to women-led companies in 2024

Source: PitchBook, October 2024, N= around 3,550 companies, with yearly fluctuations

7

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

GEN

DEX

GENDEX's Foundational Hypothesis

1

There is a lack of diversity in the Deep Tech sectors within the scope of the EIC

2

The lack of diversity at the investment stage stems from a lack of diversity at the earlier stages of the pipeline

3

Even when investment is secured, women receive terms that are less favourable than those offered to men.

4

The investment gap between women and men highlights an opportunity to expand the pool of deep tech founders

8

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

GEN

DEX

2

The lack of diversity at the investment stage stems from a lack of diversity at the earlier stages of the pipeline

Limitation in the number of qualified women joining deep tech leadership and founding teams

9

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM
Source: GENDEX elaboration on Eurostat, October 2024 Annual D&I reports; institution websites, Feedback from University Diversity Teams

2

The lack of diversity at the investment stage stems from a lack of diversity at the earlier stages of the pipeline

Fewer opportunities to leverage knowledge and networks from previous experience

10

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

GENDEX's Foundational Hypothesis

- 1 There is a lack of diversity in the Deep Tech sectors within the scope of the EIC
- 2 The lack of diversity at the investment stage stems from a lack of diversity at the earlier stages of the pipeline
- 3 Even when investment is secured, women receive terms that are less favourable than those offered to men.**
- 4 The investment gap between women and men highlights an opportunity to expand the pool of deep tech founders
- 5 Closing this gap requires robust data on where disparities are most pronounced and decisive action to address them

11

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

3 Even when investment is secured, women receive terms that are less favourable than those offered to men

Longer time to raise

6 months longer (average) than men founders to sign first term sheet

Source: GENDEX Survey, August 2024, N=51 women founders in EU+UK; N= 98 men founders in EU+UK

Less favourable vesting schedules

Source: GENDEX Survey, August 2024, N=51 women founders in EU+UK; N= 98 men founders in EU+UK

12

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

3

Even when investment is secured, women receive terms that are less favourable than those offered to men

Lower valuations

Men-led companies achieved **2.4x** higher valuations than women-led companies (2014-2024 average)

Source: GENDEX analysis on a sample of a total EU+UK of around N=20,000 companies from PitchBook and N= around 8,000 companies Dealroom (Valuations for 2024 all refer to the end of October 2024 and are not representative of all the operations until the end of the year)

More down rounds in toughest years?

14% women down-rounds vs. **12%** for men in 2023 (9% average both for women-led and men-led companies, 2014-2024)

Source: GENDEX analysis on a sample of a total EU+UK of around N=20,000 companies from PitchBook and N= around 8,000 companies Dealroom

13

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

GENDEX's Foundational Hypothesis

- 1 There is a lack of diversity in the Deep Tech sectors within the scope of the EIC
- 2 The lack of diversity at the investment stage stems from a lack of diversity at the earlier stages of the pipeline
- 3 Even when investment is secured, women receive terms that are less favourable than those offered to men.
- 4 The investment gap between women and men highlights an opportunity to expand the pool of deep tech founders

14

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

4

The investment gap between women and men highlights an opportunity to expand the pool of deep tech founders

15

A greater diversity of deep tech sectors within the scope of the EIC would mean:

- 1 Expanding the available deep tech talent pool
- 2 Increased potential for innovation
- 3 Opportunity to improve business performance
- 4 Enhancing the value and competitiveness of the European ecosystem

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

Key Action Points for Policymakers

1

Get better data

- Encourage voluntary data collection from investors
- Endorse companies and investors to disclose gender-disaggregated data on a regular basis
- Encourage voluntary data collection from investors
- Promote standardised reporting frameworks

2

Reframe the narrative

- Create a repository of case studies on women-led deep tech companies, highlighting outperformance (revenue growth, funding, exits)
- Showcase women role models, starting from universities in ICT and engineering

3

Target IP

- Support more women to protect their deep tech IP through targeted education and training
- Provide financial and legal support to women inventors

4

Guarantee sustainable returns for public money

- Provide training technological tools for investors to enable them to identify and eliminate bias
- Expand networking opportunities for women founders with potential investors, mentors, and industry partners
- Expand targeted mentorship and coaching programs for women founders

Detailed actions with lead actors and direct/indirect impact timeframe are available in full Deliverable 3.3 GENDEX Data Analysis of the Gender & Diversity Index

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

Key Action Points for Investors

1

Eliminate bias

- Trial blind evaluations in a small subset of VCs; track proportion of women at each stage to identify possible bias
- Provide training on negotiation techniques

2

Seek diversity in investment committees

- **Large LPs:** insist on a minimum threshold of women decision-makers on ICs
- **VCs:** retain and promote junior women investors to decision-making roles

3

If you see bias, call it out

- Provide safe channels for founders and team members to report bias incidents
- Endorse guidelines on equitable treatment of founders

Detailed actions with lead actors and direct/indirect impact timeframe are available in full Deliverable 3.3 GENDEX Data Analysis of the Gender & Diversity Index

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

GEN DEX

© GENDEX CONSORTIUM

THE PARTNERS

Changing the way the world thinks about the effects of technology on business and society.

International Data Corporation (IDC) is the premier global market intelligence, data and events provider for the information technology, telecom and consumer technology markets.

With more than 1,300 analysts worldwide, IDC offers global, regional, and local expertise on technology and industry opportunities and trends in over 110 countries. IDC's analysis and insight helps IT professionals, business executives, and the investment community make fact-based technology decisions and achieve their key business objectives.

BluSpecs is a consultancy firm helping clients harness the power of advanced technologies to support digital transformation. Our mission is to help clients remain relevant in an age of disruption by enhancing core business value through a mix of cyber-physical capabilities, assets and channels. BluSpecs offers a range of services from strategic positioning to technology adoption, combining analytical skills with creativity and global network connections.

Our 3 areas of focus are:

- **Strategy & ecosystems:** Assisting clients in crafting new ways to position themselves and offer value, leveraging new technologies and diverse global ecosystems
- **Tech, policy & skills:** Working with global policymakers to design and deliver impactful programs for inclusive growth in the digital economy and with corporates to provide tech briefs that analyse the latest regulations and standards
- **Industry & data:** Helping industries become more resilient and sustainable through technology and data-enabled solutions

Founderland is a non-profit organisation on a mission to build a new, intersectional and inclusive standard for entrepreneurship in Europe and the UK by building a peer community and opening access to investment for women founders who have faced obstacles tied to their race or ethnicity on their business journeys. Doing so creates diverse new representations of entrepreneurship for the next generation of women.